

Running Head: EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY
ACHIEVEMENT

**EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT
OF A GROUP OF BOYS AT TWO RURAL PRIMARY SCHOOLS IN
JAMAICA.**

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Table of Contents

ABSTRACT	IV
Chapter 1	1
Introduction and Background	1
Research Rationale	7
Purpose of Study	8
Significance of Study	8
Definition of Key Terms	9
Chapter 2	10
Literature Overview and Rationale for Theoretical framework	10
The Nature/Nurture Theory	11
Motivation and Boys Literacy Engagement	15
Boys' Attitudes and Perceptions	18
Parental Involvement	19
Teacher Competence, Attitude and knowledge	21
Contending Arguments on Boys Literacy achievement	27
Chapter 3	28
Methodology Overview	28
Research Design	28
The Pilot	29
Research Sites	30
Sample	31
Participants	31
Profile of Teacher Participants	33
Data Collection Methods	34
Ethical Considerations	36
Reliability and Validity	39
Data Analysis	40
Chapter 4	44
Introduction	44

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

Overview of findings	44
Research Question 1	45
Theme: Boys' Literacy Underachievement	45
Research Questions 2	50
Theme: Boys' Negative Attitude	50
Theme: The Nurther/ Nature Influence	51
Theme: Parental Aptitude and Attitudes	54
Research Question 3	57
Theme: Boys' Perceptions	57
Research Question 4	60
Theme: Teacher Practice	60
Sub-Theme: Perceptions of and Approaches to Assessment	60
Sub-Theme: Teacher focus: Students Needs or the Curriculum?	62
Sub-Theme: Teaching Writing: Perceptions, Attitudes and Competence	72
Summary	74
Chapter 5	75
Report Summary	75
Summary of Findings	76
Research Question 1	76
Research Question 2	76
Research Question 3	77
Research Question 4	78
Conclusion	78
Implications	79
Recommendations	80
Limitations	82
References	83
APPENDIX 1	106
APPENDIX 2	107
APPENDIX 3	108
APPENDIX 4	109
APPENDIX 5	111
APPENDIX 6	113

Table of Figures

Figure 1. 1.This figure shows the overall percentile performance for both sexes at Castle Bridge Primary for 2014-2019	47
Figure 2. 1.This figure shows Castle Bridge Primary Percentile ‘within Gender’ Performance for Boys (2014-2019)	49
Figure 2. 2. This figure shows Matthew Hall Primary ‘Within Gender’ Performance for Boys (2009-2018).....	49
Figure 3. 1.Figure shows Matthew Hall Primary’s GSAT Performance for Boys (2013-2015).....	68
Figure 3.2. Figure shows Matthew Hall Primary’s GSAT Performance for Boys (2016-2018)	69

ABSTRACT**Exploring Perspectives on the Literacy Achievement of a Group of Boys at the Two Rural Primary Schools.**

Yonae Donald

High levels of literacy within a country translates to personal and national stability. The converse would mean societal demise. Within some quarters on the international and local level, the literacy performance of boys has been the source of much panic. In other quarters, this is a case of ‘much ado about nothing’. The contradicting responses to boys’ literacy achievement, coupled with the potential social ramifications of literacy underachievement were the forces propelling this qualitative case study research. Hence the purpose of this research was to explore perspectives on the literacy achievement of a group of boys at two primary schools so as to arrive at a holistic picture of their literacy achievement. Two rural primary schools were used as the data gathering sites. Two literacy facilitators, two classroom teachers and eight boys were used as participants. Interviews, observations and document analysis were the data gathering agents.

The study revealed two main findings. First, the attitudes, perceptions and competence level of parents, teachers, school administrators and ministry officials directly influence boys’ literacy achievement. This finding has implications for the kinds of training provided for those in the education field. The main recommendation was the need for tailored professional training programmes for

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

these stakeholders in order to orchestrate the kinds of environment for boys' literacy development. Also, the data analyzed seem to suggest that boys' literacy performance may not be as dismal as is touted. However, since the data used to arrive at this conclusion was limited, a longitudinal research would be required to provide a more concrete response.

Keywords: literacy, literacy achievement, literacy underachievement and perspectives

Chapter 1

Introduction and Background

“Mis mi no laik riid. Mis ,mi no laik rait. Dat a fi gorl. Dem de sinting de a at op mi hed. Mi prifa plie baal.”

These were the expressions of a fourteen-year-old male teen with whom I had interaction about seventeen years ago. This was my first window into the psyche of one young man as to his attitude towards literacy, and primarily towards reading and writing. His utter disdain for such activities sent shock waves which ricocheted through my body. His words resonate to this day.

This scenario recounted has become like a frozen torture chamber scene from a horror movie. Over the years, the actors on the stage have changed, but the script remains the same: the squirms, the whining, the knitted brows, the protests and the engagement in mischief to get an excuse to leave the class during reading and writing activities, is reflective of the sheer contempt for reading and writing by boys. Why? Why boys? What is the genesis of this problem? Is the education system at the root of the problem? Are parents to be blamed? Did this seeming boys' crisis begin prior to high school? These questions kept churning in my head for years. I needed answers.

A critical examination of this complex phenomenon, reveals that the question of boys' literacy achievement has been a long standing issue. As early as the 17th century, documented research revealed that there was a literacy achievement gap between boys and girls (Coles & Hall, 2002; Jones &

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

Myhill,2004). But, for a while, there was a paucity of data on the phenomenon in scholarly writings. Recently however, the phenomenon has resurfaced in an unprecedented manner, jolting many stakeholders in the education system and provoking widespread debates, especially in the public and professional sphere. For many, the issue of boys' literacy achievement (primarily in reading and writing) at the primary level is an area of grave concern.

In Jamaica, the wave of anxiety experienced by the wider society is not unfounded, as a worrying trend has emerged from the grade three reading and comprehension tests as well as the grade four literacy tests. Statistical data as far as 2002 on the grade three reading and comprehension tests reveal boys' underachievement in literacy. For 2003 in particular, boys' performance was especially dismal, with only 28% of them attaining mastery. A similar pattern of underachievement was replicated in the grade four literacy examination for that year with 70.4% of girls attaining mastery, in contrast to a mere 45% of boys (Taskforce on Educational Reform Report,2004). There seems to be no reversal of the wave of underachievement for boys for this examination, as statistics extending from 2011 to 2017 reveal percentile differences as high as 22% between the genders ("Literacy, numeracy results," 2018; Reid, 2012). It comes as little surprise that Lewis (2010) in reference to performance in this examination cited several Caribbean researcher including Miller (1994) who associated the descriptor of 'struggling reader' to boys.

Boys' literacy attainment has and continues to derail national targets. Among the education targets outlined in the Taskforce on Educational Reform

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

Report (2004) was that of 100% literacy of students up to the secondary level. This was later qualified by a statement which pointed to the target as being ambitious. That this statement turned out to be self –fulfilling prophecy was revealed a decade later. In a sectorial presentation for the 2014/2015 period, under the theme ‘Student Achievement’, the then Minister of Education highlighted that the country was on the path to meeting the 100% mastery in literacy across the primary level. However, she nuanced the statement by saying that the girls were leading the charge, with boys lagging behind (Sectorial Presentation,2014).

The issue of boys’ underachievement in literacy is a pressing dilemma even in first world countries which boasts considerable economic prowess. For example, during the past decade, there has been much investigation by key stakeholders into gender and literacy performance. The documented findings have been used as a basis for the implementation of various strategies to improve boys’ literacy performance. Such endeavors have yielded limited success as the literacy gap persists, unabated (Younger & Warrington, 2005 as cited by Booth & Elliot –Johns,2009). The studies of Abdullah and Mohd- Asraf (2016), and Clarke 2016 echoed similar findings.

Furthermore, Scott (2012) speaks to the attitudes and perceptions of boys to writing within the United States. For many boys, the word ‘writing’ is synonymous with solitary confinement. It is perceived as an activity which isolates them from their peers. This aversion to writing is a common thread which runs through American schools and is a worldwide phenomenon. Boys in general are found to display high levels of writing apprehension. Writing apprehension is

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

defined as a “general avoidance of writing and of situations perceived by the individual to potentially require some amount of writing accompanied by the potential for evaluation of that writing” (Daley,1979, p.37). Scott (2012) further notes that writing apprehension has an inimical impact on scholastic achievement, self-image and even career decisions in life.

It is an undisputed fact that literacy is fundamental to learning and is a gateway to longitudinal academic success (Lewis ,2010). Boys who fail to develop the requisite literacy skills at the primary level find themselves in a precarious situation. In anchoring this line of reasoning, Gove and Wetterberg (2011) opines that children who fall behind early, stay behind later on. In cementing the connection between low literacy achievement among boys at the primary level and subsequent underachievement at the high school level, the Education Reform Taskforce Report (2004) cites Janet Quello and Beverley Carlson in their assessment of the ROSE programme as saying that “the most critical problem at the primary level [is that of] students reading ability” (p.95). This problem is said to be “concentrated among boys” (p.95) .This extends into high school where up to grade nine a high percentage of students, predominantly boys, can either not read or write, or are “functionally illiterate” (p.95). This deficiency is said to impair overall academic performance. Edmund- Woods (2011) expands this idea by noting that within the regional context, such boys fail to attain the minimum of five CXC subjects.

Such a situation of underachievement in exit examinations is mirrored within the Jamaican context. As early as 2004, the Task force on Educational

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

Reform (2004) reported that in terms of gender performance in exit exams as CSEC, girls have an established pattern of outperforming boys in most areas. Moreover, the Ministry of Education, Youth and Culture, (2018) document disclosed that for 2018, of the 34 subjects sat in CSEC, girls outperformed boys in all areas except chemistry and biology. For these two subjects, there were marginal percentile differences of 2% and 3%. It little wonder that on the local soil, newspaper headlines as “We need to rescue our boys” and “We need to save our boys”, have become like tattoos etched in the Jamaican fabric. These statements aptly picture the precarious situation in which Jamaica finds itself.

Moreover, research has established a longstanding association between boys’ low literacy competence at the primary level and subsequent low educational attainment at all levels of the education ladder (Antilla,2013; Clark,2012 ;Common Wealth Policy Brief, 2017; Education Reform Taskforce Report, 2004; George et al.,2009; Vision 2020 Jamaica,2009; Wilson,2016). Furthermore, Lewis (2010) points to literacy as the “gateway subject which if not acquired at a proficient level can undermine a child’s successful experience of school, which in turn has implications for his/her future employment” (p.24). For Edmund –Woods (2011) this has personal and societal ramifications, as boys who fail to attain literacy proficiency, find themselves unable to access viable employment options later on in life. This leads them to seek economic refuge on the wrong side of the law.

In this shifting global economy, acquiring tertiary level education credentials is crucial to securing economic stability. Within the Jamaican context, there is a

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

serious gender imbalance in this regard. This imbalance which is skewed in favour of females, reflects Jamaica's grim reality. For example, enrollment for HEART dating back to 2004/2005 showed a female majority of 58% (HEART Trust, n.d). Further, statistical data released by LMIP (2019) on student enrollment for the period 2011-2019 reveals a female majority of 53%. Moreover, although 47% of the cohort was male, only 36% received certification. Interestingly for this period, only 39% of the total cohort successfully completed their programmes and received certification. Of this number, males represented 17%. While a number of mitigating factors could have contributed to this dismal male representation, it seems profound that the USAID (2019) lists 'inability to meet academic requirements' as the foremost factor.

Statistical data available on gender enrollment in other tertiary institutions is a matter of national concern. For example, according to USAID (2011) as far back as 2004, data on student enrolment in 32 tertiary level institutions across Jamaica revealed that males represented 37% of the cohort. Statistical data was also analyzed in relation to UTECH and The University of the West Indies. For example, in the 2014 annual report, the University of technology disclosed a consistent trend of male under-representation for a twelve-year period commencing 2002. The data revealed differences in male enrollment which compared to females as high as 18% between 2011 and 2013. There, however was a slight narrowing of the gap by 2% in 2014. The widest gap existed at the doctoral and master's level, where females represented 65.3% of the cohort for 2013/2014 (The University of Technology, 2014). Moreover, the statistical review

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

prepared by the UWI for the academic periods 2012/2013 and 2016/2017 revealed that for most faculties across the four campuses, males represented between 15.7% and 36.8% of the cohort. Moreover, a statistical review of student enrollment between 1948 and 2017 indicated that female enrollment tripled that of males (The University of the West Indies,2018).

The forgoing discussion is indicative of a crisis in terms of male academic attainment. Its genesis seems to be tangled with boys' literacy underachievement at the primary level.

Research Rationale

The foregoing, points to males “threatening to become a permanent underclass” (USAID,2011, p. 4). Such a dilemma has personal, social and economic ramifications within the Jamaican context. This includes the loss of human capital and a failure to nurture and develop active citizenship, which stymies the countries' sustainable development agenda (Rintaningrum,2009; The World Bank ,2008). Undergirding this argument is Lewis (2010) who postulates that “high levels of literacy have been associated with human rights, poverty reduction, sustainable development...empowerment, gender equality, among other human indices” (p.24). Hence, literacy levels among learners, should be a matter of national concern. Therefore, the wave of literacy underachievement among boys within the Jamaican context, necessitates urgent investigation and analysis.

Purpose of Study

The purpose of this qualitative study is to explore perspectives on the literacy achievement of a group of boys at two rural primary schools in Jamaica. The main question is: What are the perspectives on the literacy achievement of a group of boys at two rural primary schools in Jamaica?

The sub-questions are:

1. What are the perspectives of teachers on the literacy achievement a group of boys at two rural primary schools?
2. How do teachers describe their experiences in developing the reading and writing skills of boys at two rural primary school?
3. How do boys at two primary schools perceive their literacy achievement?
4. What has been the experiences of boys with reading and writing development?

Significance of Study

The study is significant as it will add to the existing body of literature and especially that of the local context where there is a dearth of data. The study will also prove beneficial within my teaching context, as the insights will be used to formulate targeted intervention programmes to improve boys' literacy achievement. School administrations should also find the study useful as it identifies specific areas in which literacy teachers require administrative and professional support. It will also provide parents with insight into the issue and the need to create support systems to improve boys' literacy achievement. For

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

policy makers, having recent data reflecting the Jamaican context, will enable them to frame policies which are more sound and which better address the literacy needs of boys. For literacy coaches and literacy specialists outside of my teaching context, it is hoped that this research will trigger further large-scale inquiry into the phenomenon to improve practice on the local and regional level.

Definition of Key Terms

Literacy: Literacy is the ability, confidence and willingness to engage with language, to acquire, construct and communicate meanings in all aspects of daily living. It also now includes “digital, electronic, and visual expressions” (Gentry & McAdams 2013.p.1).

Literacy Achievement: This refers to ones’ performance or attainment in relation to national literacy standards or benchmarks(USAID,2016).

Literacy Underachievement: This refers performance or attainment which is below national literacy standards or benchmarks (USAID,2016).

Perspective: This is a particular way of thinking, a point of view or attitude towards people and things. Ones’ perspective is influenced by ones’ belief or experiences (Collins English Dictionary, n.d).

Chapter 2

Literature Overview and Rationale for Theoretical framework

The literature offers multiple, complex and contradictory responses to boys' literacy achievement. For some bodies of literature, boys' literacy achievement is linked to factors as the nature/nurture theory, boys' attitudes and perceptions, teacher practice and levels of parental involvement. For another set, boys' literacy achievement is at a crisis level. However, there are some bodies of literature which vigorously contest the notion of boys' underachievement on the basis that this is not supported by facts. In view of this discrepancy, there is a need to investigate with a wide open aperture to ensure that a holistic picture within the Jamaican context emerges. To facilitate this, the research is undergirded by the theory of constructivism.

This theory advances that knowledge is social construct. Hence, the notion of 'truth' or one's sense of reality, is framed within the parameters set by one's environment (Fosnot ,2005; Zydney, Renniger, Hai-Jew & List ,2012;). Vygotsky (1962) canvases this point by highlighting that this socio- cultural framework runs deep into the human psyche, influencing the mental processes.

This theory thereby interrogates the notion of absolutism of truth and advances the concept of parallel realities in operation. The central endeavor of the constructivist approach therefore is to 'get into the head of the subjects being studied' and to understand their interpretation of truth (Creswell ,2008; Kivunja &Kuyini, 2017).

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

Further, constructivists advocate for learners to be active participants in matters which affect them (Dagar & Yadav ,2016). This essentially gives them a voice. This theoretical frame-work seeks to establish this precedence, by orchestrating the kind of platform which enables boys to participate in an investigation which directly involves and impacts them.

The Nature/Nurture Theory

One of the earliest tenets as to the origin of the boys' literacy crisis is that of the nature theory. Such a theory seeks to explain boys' language development. It is underpinned by the ideology that the brains of females are biologically wired to outperform males in the earlier stages, in language related tasks as reading and writing. Eventually though, there would be a narrowing of the achievement gap as boys mature (Biddulph 2008).

However, sceptics have contested this age old hypotheses, describing it as dangerous and absurd. For example, Whitehead (2011) advocates that it is fatal to boys' literacy achievement, as pedagogy supported by this theory dooms them to a fate of underachievement at the primary level. Further, one major deficit fingered by other bodies of literature is the lack of empirical evidence that boys are hard-wired to underperform in literacy in the formative years and that the literacy achievement gap between the sexes narrows as boys mature. For the former, research into human brains reveal its plasticity or malleability. Hence, one's brain is not 'hardwired' but can be 'rewired' by one's experiences, especially during the formative years (Elliot 2009). For the later, evidence points

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

to an unabated widening of the literacy gap (Lynn & Mikk ,2009; Kaiser, Haller, Schmitz & Nitsch,2009; Reynolds, Scheiber, Hajovsky, Schwartz, & Kaufman, 2015).

By challenging the biological theory, the aforementioned bodies of literature have spawned nature vs nurture debate. According to the nature theory, boys will naturally steer away from literacy activities as they are psychologically conditioned to believe that engaging in such activities will strip them of their masculinity. Such a belief system is wired into boys' psyche through social interactions during their formative years. As conditioned beings, boys are taught that masculinity is synonymous with being tough, rebellious, and daring. Reading and writing do not fit into these kinds of associations (Abdullah & Mohd-Asraf, 2016; Canadian Council on Reading, 2009; Edwards & Jones,2018; Scott,2012).

Dutro (2001) however, posits a slight variance in perspective regarding reading as a gendered activity. While Dutro (2001) takes the stance that gender stereotypes are deeply entrenched during the formative years, the argument is advanced that boys do not perceive reading in itself as a gendered activity but views certain kinds of texts as gender specific. Hence, according to this argument, boys do not have an aversion to reading, but their choice of materials is hemmed in by socially constructed boundaries.

The nurther theory has also taken deep root in the education sphere, informing much of its reforms. However, various researchers have risen against such a practice. For example, Kehler and Martino (2007) question the effectiveness of approaches that rely on evoking socially constructed gender

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

differences as a basis for reform in schools. The result of such an approach has only served to intensify the problem. It has bred the myth that what is said to be 'natural' behaviour, which translates to negative attitudes in boys towards literacy, is innate. Such a misconception has led to ill-advised educational policies as calling for more male teachers in the classroom and the employment of single sex classrooms. However, these initiatives have only served to sustain deeply entrenched cultural assumptions about gender differences (Alloway,2007). As a result, much of the literature challenging the nature theory have called on the education sector to interrogate and challenge gender binaries instead of nurturing them. Failing to challenge the gender binaries leads to the creation of a false 'binary dichotomy' which treats boys as a homogeneous group and ignores their individual needs and differences (Abdullah & Mohd-Asraf 2016; Barbousas & Velluto ,2017).

The argument is also promoted that teachers play a significant role in perpetuating and sustaining boys' literacy underachievement as they have bought into the socially contrived ideology of gender stereotypes. For example, George et al. (2009) conducted an investigation into boys' academic underachievement within the context of Trinidad and Tobago. Much attention was given to boys' literacy performance in reading and writing as these were found to have the most impact on overall academic achievement. What was noted was that gender stereotyping was strongly ingrained into the narrative of that society. This was so embedded into the psyche of educators that instead of investigating and interrogating the underlying reasons behind boys' literacy underachievement,

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

many teachers simply assented to the idea that this was the norm. The failure of teachers to implement corrective pedagogical measures to address literacy deficiencies has served as a catalyst for boys' literacy underachievement.

Corroborating this line of reasoning are Edwards and Jones (2018) and Brown (2015). According to Edmonds and Jones (2018), educators' vision has been rendered so obscure by social conditioning, that they can only 'see' their students through the lens of gender. Brown (2015) anchors this point with a quote from a teacher who prefaced the discussion on boys writing with the statement: "He is the typical boy, and boys do not really like to write... It is hard to get boys to produce a piece of writing, but that is okay because they are just doing what all boys do" (. p.5). In relation to the reading practices of both genders, another teacher said: "I would imagine the girls probably read more... [boys] probably don't like reading (Edwards & Jones ,2018, p.4).

Moreover, the research of Edwards and Jones (2018) reveal two contrasting findings. First, when teachers promote the gendered perception that boys are inherently underachievers in literacy, this is often mirrored in boys' literacy performance. As a result, boys absolve themselves of taking responsibility for their learning and the subsequent lowered achievement becomes a 'self-fulfilling prophecy' which has perpetuated a culture of male despondency. Conversely, in learning contexts where gender stereotyping is less accentuated and boys are treated as individuals, healthier learning environments are evident.

Scott (2012) however takes a different stance and opines that social constructs of masculinity need not be perceived as a death sentence for boys'

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

literacy development, but rather as a gateway to bridging the gap between what obtains for boys' present literacy practices and their untapped potential. Williams (2004) as cited by Scott (2012) postulates that there is a deep connection between writing and one's social identity. Boys associate masculinity (and its accompanying patterns of thought and behaviour) with their gender and most importantly their identity. As such, their compositions represent their social identities etched on paper. Hence, they should be valued by teachers. Thus, when planning and critiquing boys' literacy creations, teachers should take into account what it means to be masculine. Orchestrating this kind of non-threatening environment where boys feel valued and motivated will go a far way in reversing the culture of male despondency.

Motivation and Boys Literacy Engagement

The aforementioned discussion points to an important theme which keeps emerging: that of motivation. In some arenas, the thinking is that boys are disadvantaged as they operate in environments which are hostile to the genre of literature they prefer to read as well as their preferences for writing. It is argued that this has dealt a fatal blow to boys' literacy development.

As it relates to reading, the argument is touted that there is a great disparity in the genre preferences of both sexes. Girls are said to prefer narrative fiction, while boys are more inclined towards comics, sequels, science fiction and graphic action packed texts. The argument is stridently advanced that genres preferred by boys are perceived as inappropriate forms of school based materials.

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

Since the teaching profession is female dominated, the preferences of this gender is reflected in the books and materials selected for content in literacy classrooms (Barbousas & Velluto, 2017; The Canadian Council on Learning, 2009). The glaring reality of this situation is reflected by George et al. (2009) whose research reflects the Caribbean context. The article pinpoints boys' disengagement with reading and demands the use of diversified texts to appeal to boys.

In reinforcing this position, Mead (2012), McGeown et al. (2015) and Hughes- Hassel, Bartley and Koehler (2010) postulate that there is direct correlation between reading attitudes and reading achievement. A critical determinant of boys' attitude towards reading is motivation. The motivating factor for boys to engage in reading is being given the opportunity to select books based on their reading preferences and which allows them to make personal connections. Such personal connections are essential to peaking and sustaining interest levels in reading. This will create the proper breeding ground for more meaningful literacy engagement on the part of boys. As boys see themselves mirrored in the books they are presented with, they feel a sense of inclusion and are thus more enticed into continuing the story. Moreover, they can make more text-to-self, text-to-text, and text-to-world connections (Landt (2013). This leads to sustained lifelong reading habits (Logan & Johnson, 2009).

In examining the issue of writing and engaging boys, Dutro (2006) as cited by Scott (2012) voiced the need for boys to be allowed to write about things that are important to them as this "allows them to share their passions, thus creating a more meaningful experience, heightening the engagement, and

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

allowing for a deeper understanding to be absorbed” (p.14). Cementing this stance is Anderson’s (2003) study as cited by Scott (2012) which reveals that when boys were forced to write on topics dictated by the teacher, they “wrote the minimum amount required... sometimes less,” [and their] “writing was flat with little or no voice or description” (p.14). In sharp contrast, when given the choice to write what was important to them, they are more motivated and the end products were infused with life, voice, and excitement.

Further, when teachers allow students to write from the perspective of self, they are facilitating what Pearl (1980) refers to as sense-self or an inner connection with the topic. The deeper the sense –self, the more meaningful the engagement with writing. Further, Emig (1977) postulates that the concept of ‘self’ cannot be divorced from the writing process, as writing is a highly personal act. Hence, if boys are not allowed to write from the perspective of self or issues with which they have personal connections, then essentially their voices will be silenced and there will be no motivation to write.

Boys' Attitudes and Perceptions

The worrying message echoed in many scholarly writings is that boys' attitudes and perceptions negatively impact their levels of literacy engagement. This inevitably impacts their achievement.

Hyatt (2002) posits that many boys have a negative attitude towards school based writing and are reluctant writers. Millard's (2002) study reveals that even competent writers dislike most school-based writing. Clarke (2012) cements these findings, adding that that some boys did not value reading as an activity and as such did not seek out opportunities for reading. Further, Clarke's (2016) study reveals that boys perceive girls as more successful writers and readers. This is mirrored in their attitudes and literacy output.

The idea also emerges that boys' abhorrence for writing directly influences their levels of independent writing engagement (Meuriso –Storm ,2006). Hyatt's (2002) study shows that only 15.2% of boys engage in such. Even as it relates to writing using technology formats as text messages, messages on social media and instant messages, Clarke (2016) finds that girls engage in this form of literacy practice more than boys.

Further, Muszak (2016) and Clarke (2012) highlight that there are low levels of independent reading engagement on the part of boys. For example, many boys do not seek out opportunities for reading as visiting the library, but opt instead to engage in recreational activities. This is found to directly impact reading achievement.

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

Atkinson (2009) and Blair and Sanford (2004) offer a viable explanation for boys' disengagement with school based literacy. They posit that many boys who display an aversion for in-school literacy often engaged in literacy practices outside of school. For many, there is a glaring gap between school based literacy and real life. As it relates to reading in particular, boys perceive school based reading as 'artificial', lacking authentic connections to their realities. Such boys engage with what is termed as 'life reading' or literacy content outside of school which finds connection with their interests and their cultural realities.

Parental Involvement

There has been much exploration into the link between parental involvement and children's literacy achievement. Much of this research advocate that there is a social dimension to literacy. For example, Mirra, Filipiak, and Garcia (2015) posit that "literacy is not a discipline limited to academic skill development, but as a competency that connects us and other people and to society as the source of all communication and social action" (p.3). Further, Nehal (2017) and Compton-Lily, (2009) postulate that the first social interaction occurs within the precincts of homes. Parents are the child's first teachers and agents of socialization. Hence the quality of parent /child social interactions is a critical determinant in literacy development.

DeBaryshe, Binder and Buell (2000) as cited by Simmonds (2012) extends this line of argument by stressing that the home is the perfect soil for literacy development to take root as "it provides the opportunities to observe literacy

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

activities with others, engage in joint literacy activities and independently explore literacy materials and behaviors” (p.17). Further Gest, Freeman, Domitrovich and Welsh, (2004) and Nehal (2017) argue that parents who provide literacy rich environments and who are involved with their children in literacy tasks not only stimulate their children’s linguistic development as it relates to vocabulary and syntax, but also language comprehension and expressive language skills as well.

The reality brought forward in some literature is that some parents shy away from active participation in their children’s literacy development (Eskelä-Haapanen et al.,2018). In speaking to what obtains for children’s literacy development when there is the absence of the parent element, Stanovich (1986) states that this creates what is called the Matthew effect. The Matthew effect highlights the vast reading gap between those who are supported and those who are not. For the latter, competency is developed and sustained, while for the former, growth is stagnated.

Various factors have been espoused to explain levels of parental involvement. Foremost, parental involvement is determined by their sense of self-efficacy. Ice & Hoover-Dempsey (2010) summarize self-efficacy as “a person’s belief that he or she can act in ways that are likely to produce desired outcomes” (p.344). For some parents, low literacy levels evoke a low sense of self-efficacy. Nehal (2017) found that parents’ perceptions of their skill -set impacts the types of literacy activities they engage in with their children as well as the children’s level of exposure to texts in their homes. Nehal (2017) also suggests that parents with low education might shy away from active parent

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

/school partnership as they feel uncomfortable because of the lack of ability to communicate with the teacher and the feeling of inadequacy when in the company of other parents with higher education.

Moreover, Hoover-Dempsey and Sandler (1997) emphasize that parents' beliefs and perceptions of their role in their children's literacy development are high determinants of levels of involvement. As it relates to parent role construction, parents are more likely to actively support and guide the literacy development of their children if they perceive their role as critical in this regard. In connection to belief systems, Simmonds (2012) reports that when parents have a positive view of reading and place value on the activity, they are more likely to engage in literacy activities with their children and further support learning through parent/ school partnerships. Nehal (2017) concludes that parents' attitudes dictated by their belief systems as well as perceptions of their roles will either fuel or asphyxiate their children's literacy progress.

Teacher Competence, Attitude and knowledge

Another thinking as to the root of the boys' literacy underachievement is that schools have unwittingly become conspirators to the crisis. A general lack of understanding of composition, weak pedagogy, narrow understanding of assessment and the failure to recognize the legitimacies of multiliteracies are said to form the core of the problem.

One of the concepts emerging out of mainstream literature is that the act of composing is a personal, recursive, complex, and highly cognitive process

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

(Graham,2019; Uusen,2009). According Emig (1977) and Pearl (1980) the act of composing begins within the brain with a mental blueprint for what is later engraved on paper. The mental blueprint must then be harnessed through oral language and then represented in graphic images conveyed through the hands. This graphic representation must then be interrogated by the composer to ensure that the message being transmitted mirrors the internal blueprint and aligns to the notion of the topic. The composer's representation of the text is then re-constructed and updated cognitively through a process referred to as retrospective restructuring. This process is often replicated several times during composition until the desired product is achieved.

Not only is composition a personal act, but there is a strong social dimension to it, with the teacher and peers at its epee-centre. Olinghouse and Graham, 2009 advance the idea that writing demands high levels of abstraction. In many cases, boys struggle to 'abstract' knowledge and transcribe such into writing. Milian (2005) speaks to the teachers' role in bridging this gap through scaffolding and peer collaboration. The use of peer collaboration is a powerful vehicle which enables composers to jointly "organize the task, plan the content, articulate their views" (p.335) and engage in the process of construction and reshaping of text. This facilitates the construction of two kinds of knowledge essential to driving writing. As writers collaborate, they are simultaneously interrogating, constructing and reformulating knowledge of the writing process, while "gaining knowledge[content] to produce knowledge[content]" (Montero-Fleta & Perez-Sabater, 2011, p.622).

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

In view of the complexities involved in composing, Graham (2019) and Ambe (2013) maintain that teachers must possess high levels of understanding of the process as well as pedagogical competence to support its development. In addressing what constitutes effective writing pedagogy, Santangelo and Olinghouse (2009) state that this involves modelling, providing explicit instruction, providing students with opportunities to engage in authentic writing experiences reflective of various genres and teacher feedback in response to students' writing.

The challenge within many learning contexts however is that teachers are failing dismally at developing boys' writing competence (Graham & Rijlaarsdam, 2016). There are several situations which give rise to this problem. For Graham (2019) and Graham and Rijlaarsdam (2016) weak pedagogical skills handicaps effective writing instruction. An interrogation of classroom practice reveals that many teachers woefully lack an awareness of effective approaches to support writing competency. This results in a mismatch between learner needs and approaches employed and further alienates boys from writing.

Moreover, in some learning contexts there is a literacy imbalance. There is an over focus on reading to the demise of writing. Graham (2019) opines that the lack of knowledge about how these skills are inter-related may be at the heart of the problem. Graham (2008) notes that such knowledge is critical, as reading builds the foundation for writing. This is so as reading mimics good writing and as such provides the framework for effective composition.

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

According to Graham (2008) and Ambe (2013) lack of teacher support and training, lies at the core of the problem. In Graham's (2008) study, teachers articulated that training institutions and educational workshops failed to adequately prepare them to teach writing. For many, the content delivered was generic in nature and void of relevance to the heterogeneous contexts in they operated. This rendered them incompetent to develop students' writing skills.

Another factor postulated by Graham, Cappizi, Harris, Hebert and Morphy (2014) is that sufficient time is not dedicated to developing the art of writing. As such, writing development is significantly stifled. In a bid to explain why some teachers allocate so little time to writing, Applebee and Langer (2011) suggest that the pressure to prepare for high stake tests is the main culprit. Darwish (2016) stresses that preparation for high stake examinations and covering the curriculum are high on the agenda of many school administrations. As such, much pressure is mounted on teachers to conform to the dictated culture. In the end, pedagogical practices are more aligned to the schools' agenda instead of students' writing needs.

A long list of literature lay the blame of boys' literacy underachievement on the schools' narrow understanding of assessment. According Wongwanich and Yamtim (2013) there are low levels of assessment literacy among many educators. For many, assessment is a four letter word tantamount to test. For many, the concept of assessment is shrouded in ambiguity and is a complex and dense maize beyond the comprehension of 'mere mortals' (Popham, 2004).

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

Mertler (2003) credits this to the overemphasis on summative or high stake assessment in many schools.

A common argument surfacing is that teacher training institutions have left teachers ill-prepared to develop and use assessment to literacy development. Verberg, Tigelaar and Verloop (2015), Mertler (2003) and Mellati and Khademi (2018) reinforce the idea that this has resulted in many teachers possessing a narrow understanding of assessment. It is this superficial knowledge which has impaired teachers' ability to adequately measure learner abilities, use and interpret assessment data, and to adjust instructional practice to drive reading and writing development in meaningful ways.

It is further advanced that literacy assessment is biased towards boys and as such, unfairly positions them as underachievers (Canadian Council on Reading, 2009). Alloway (2007) and Scardamalia, Sun and Zhang (2010) argue that schools as well as the curriculum, have created the problem by failing to recognize the legitimacy of multi-literacies. As such, much of the measures used to demonstrate that boys are under-performing in relation to girls are based on a narrow definition and understanding of literacy.

In recent times, the definition of literacy has undergone a metamorphosis. Its evolution has been effected by the fluid nature of the ICT. This has redefined literacy, as it challenges the very notion of 'text' and its associated features (Kervin & Mantei,2010; Graham & Ng,2017; Sang,2017).

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

The broadening and deepening of the definition of literacy has given birth a new concept, that of multiliteracies. Boche (2014) postulates that the concept of multiliteracies demands the modification of classroom pedagogy in tandem with the changing demands of society to ably equip 21st century learners to thrive in a globalized society. Since society is largely technologically driven, learning and how it is assessed must take place within this framework.

However, some educators have failed to recognize the legitimacy of multiliteracies in favour of archaic methodologies (Picton ,2019). Common barriers to practitioners embracing the new face of literacy and how it is approached and assessed include low levels of digital literacy, low sense of self efficacy and inadequate training in effectively infusing technology with practice. Picton's (2019) survey revealed that teachers have a stronger sense of self-efficacy when using technology for personal rather than professional use. Many reported that they lacked training in using technology to develop literacy. Kivunja (2014) aptly describes many educators as 'digital immigrants' in a world surrounded by 'digital natives' or learners who command high levels of digital fluency. In fact, Alloway (2007) and Scardamalia et al. (2010) emphasize that in the context of this digital age, boys command higher levels of digital competency than girls and many engage in out of school literacy practices not valued by teachers. It is this disjuncture between their out of school literacy practices and those literacy practices recognized by schools which unfairly positions them as underachievers in literacy.

Contending Arguments on Boys Literacy achievement

There are however bodies of literature which seek to challenge the notion of all boys underachieving in literacy. They aggressively contend this idea on the basis that it is a gross exaggeration of reality (Alloway, 2007; Berrill & Martino, 2003; Geske & Ozola, 2009; Landt, 2013). Further, Muszak (2016) argues that much of the literature fixated on boys' literacy achievement are bent on propagating negative data, and have conveniently ignored the many triumphs of boys in literacy. Moreover, Berrill and Martino (2003) and Geske and Ozola, (2009) forward the stance that underachievement in literacy is not innate. The argument advanced is that boys' literacy achievement extends way beyond the frontiers of gender. Several factors have been presented as factors contributing to boys' literacy achievement. First, achievement is linked parents' education status. Second, emergent literacy directly impacts literacy achievement. Third, boys level of engagement in literacy practices impact their achievement.

Chapter 3

Methodology Overview

This chapter introduces the methodology for this qualitative research. It outlines, the research design, the pilot, sample, participants, data collection methods, data analysis procedure, ethical considerations and measures to establish trustworthiness, reliability and credibility.

Research Design

As an interpretive researcher, I am opposed to the notion of a concrete reality. Reality is malleable, as it is socially and culturally constructed. Hence a qualitative case design facilitates the fluid nature of reality (Maxwell,2012; Rahman,2016). Further, the topic under consideration naturally lends itself to a qualitative case study design. keywords in the topic as ‘exploring’ and ‘perspectives’ are indicative of the need for deep exploration into the phenomenon on a level which cannot be quantified. Further, this approach enabled me to understand the phenomenon through the varied lens of students and teachers. Such varied perspectives of reality facilitated a wide angle view of boy’s literacy achievement (Zaidah ,2007).

Further, this approach allowed for exploration of the phenomenon in the participants’ natural setting (Fraenkel &Wallen ,2008). As such, it lessened inhibitions and facilitated my admittance into the world of these participants. Such non-threatening conditions allowed for the free flow to strong emotions,

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

experiences and thoughts, and naturally facilitated deeper probing (Creswell,2008; Yilmaz, 2013).

Finally, the use of a case study approach allowed for data gathering using several techniques (Nieuwenhuis, 2007). This allowed me to garner a variety of data. This not only facilitated the triangulation process, but allowed me to map and connect emerging ideas as well as to identify anomalies from the data and to probe these to find answers (Vissak,2010) Hence, this approach allowed opportunities for greater delving into the topic.

The Pilot

Prior to engaging with the field, I carried out a pilot at a rural primary school to test the rigor of the interview questions. This pilot involved one classroom teacher who was a literacy specialist, along with three grade five male students at the non-mastery, near mastery and mastery literacy levels.

The interview with the teacher yielded a wealth of information which adequately addressed the research questions. The converse was the reality with the boys. Originally, I had nine questions for the interview. In the end, the 20-minute interview yielded little information. For example, when I asked the questions: How do you view reading and or what is writing class like? The main response was “good miss”. Also, some of the questions were a bit vague. For example, the question: Describe what writing classes are like, was met with perplexed faces. I tried with limited success to elicit in-depth responses to most of

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

the questions. The pilot revealed the need to make adjustments to the interview questions so as to yield more robust data.

Research Sites

Creswell (2008) indicates that purposive selection should be applied to choice of site. In line with this, two rural primary schools were chosen with strong concentrations of boys at various reading and writing levels. Thus, they were rich sources to gather authentic data.

The first site was Matthew Hall primary. It is located near a bustling town centre. It has a student population of 590, with a male majority of 306. The teacher cohort is 36. The school has a specialized programme to support those struggling with literacy. A three-member literacy specialist team (including a grade four teacher) supervises the programme. There are 30 girls and 70 boys in this programme. The students are assisted three times weekly for 30 to 45 minutes for each session. With support from the literacy team, regular class teachers address the literacy needs of those outside of the programme

Castle Bridge primary is located on a hilly terrain overlooking a farming community. The school's population stands at 75 students, with 31 of these being male. 41% of the students read below their expected level. Of this number, 58% are boys. One literacy specialist provides remedial support for such learners. Each group receives three 45 to 60 minutes' of remedial literacy weekly.

Sample

The non- probability purposive sampling was employed for this study. This sampling method is used when individuals are intentionally selected to provide information that cannot be garnered from other sources (Alvi, 2016; Taherdoost,2016). This method is most appropriate as data required for this research is only available from primary school teachers and male students at that level (Alkassim, Musa & Sulaiman,2015; Sharma, 2017). Moreover, this kind of sampling was convenient, as the schools are located in my environs. Thus, data was readily and easily had.

Participants

Creswell (2008) posits that purposive sampling is applicable to participant choice in qualitative research. As such, I selected participants who could best provide an in-depth picture of boy's literacy achievement at the primary level. Thereby, twelve individuals were selected from two rural primary schools. They included, two literacy specialists, two class teachers from grades four and six, and eight boys, five from grade four and three from grade six. I approached the research through the lens of both teacher and student to ensure that the findings were balanced, reflective of a multiplicity of perspectives. This was in line with my theoretical framework, which advances that there are manifolds of truth or reality.

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

Further, of the two teacher participants chosen from each site, one was a literacy specialist and other a class teacher. Since no two learning context is homogeneous and even within a given school context, various learning situations can be reflected, the choice of two teachers offered a wider snapshot of not only the literacy achievement of the male population but of the literacy practices embedded in them. Also, the two participants provided a sense of balance as it relates to the achievement of all boys. This is so as the literacy specialist is assigned to underachievers in literacy, while the class teacher would interface with boys at all literacy levels.

Eight boys ranging from ages nine to twelve were chosen as student participants. They were chosen from the grade four and grade six cohort based on the three performance profile for literacy: mastery, near mastery and non-mastery. The official grade four literacy record as well as the IDRI records were used as a basis for identifying and choosing the participants. Choosing boys who fell in each category ensured that the data collected represented as closely as possible the collective perspectives of boys across these institutions. Further, the boys were chosen from the classes of the teacher participants. Selecting boys who interfaced with these participants enabled further triangulation of data from teacher interviews and observations. Moreover, this unique point of entry into each context, provided in-depth understanding into their perspectives of such contexts and how these impacted their literacy achievement.

Profile of Teacher Participants

Mrs. Beans has been a literacy facilitator for seven years. She holds a degree in Special Education. During her career she has supported struggling learners (mainly boys) across the school population. She spear-heads the literacy team of three teachers and has initiated numerous support programmes for students, parents and staff.

Mrs. Brown holds a degree in literacy. She has 17 years of teaching experiences, with fifteen years as a class teacher at the grade four level. She prepares male dominated groups for the grade four literacy and PEP examinations.

Mrs. Blacks holds a diploma in Special Education and a degree in Primary Education. She has taught for 18 years. Fifteen of such years has been spent at the grade six level preparing a predominantly male population for GSAT and PEP examinations.

Mrs. Johns has been a teacher for 11 years. She holds a diploma in Special Education and a degree in Literacy Studies. She has taught 9 years as a literacy facilitator and one year respectively at grade 6 and 4.

Data Collection Methods

Qualitative research employs the use of multiple methods to generate data (Nieuwenhuis, 2007). For this research, semi -structured individual and focused group interviews, observations and document analysis were the data generating agents.

The first method employed was that of observation. In my role as an unobtrusive observer of literacy sessions, I was able to engage my senses as I noticed body language, facial expressions and both listened to and viewed the interactions between participants and the boys. This kind of ‘live play’ allowed (DeMunck & Sobo, 1998), deep insights into the literacy practices rooted in such settings, as well as boys’ response to them. These observations were penned for later analysis and then used as reference points to refine interview questions.

Further, among the benefits of observation is that it allowed me to become familiar with the participants and vice- versa. This lent itself to more relaxed atmospheres which facilitated the free flow of information during the interviews which followed. (Schensul, Schensul & LeCompte, 1999).

Document analyses was another method employed. Data was obtained from official grade four literacy and GSAT result documents. The initial objective was to use the grade four literacy results only, but after the interview with the teacher participants I decided to add the GSAT data. However, because of the COVID outbreak only GSAT results from Matthew Hall primary was collected.

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

Hence a comparative analysis could not have been done to establish patterns or variances.

The Grade four literacy result data was used as empirical evidence to address the research question. First, the performance of boys in this examination for both schools were analyzed separately. Afterwards, I engaged in comparative analysis to establish areas of convergence and variance. I employed this method simultaneously with observation for data triangulation purpose (Brown, 2009) and as a solid reference point for further probing during the interview process.

The last method of data collection was the semi- structured face to face interview. According Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2000) the purpose of interviews are not just about collecting data but “it is part of life itself, its human embeddedness is inescapable” (p. 267). The semi structured interview allowed for participants to have a voice in the discussion as the nature of the questions were not static and their scope allowed participants to take charge to a great extent in expressing their views. In allowing participants to speak freely, perspectives and ideas not initially anticipated surfaced (Gray,2004). I was able to probe further into those uncharted realms and to unearth new awakenings into boys’ literacy achievement. Moreover, the face to face format was an effective tool which allowed me to observe body language and to take note of participants’ tone as they responded to questions. This too gave insights into the emotions and views of participants, especially for the boys who engaged in much gesticulation.

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

Most of the interviews were completed near the end of the data gathering process to ensure more efficient use of time. This timing also ensured that the interviews were more focused and purpose driven with the other data collection methods serving as reference points. Further, short interviews were conducted during the data analysis process for clarification purpose and to establish cohesion among the data collected.

Finally, focused group interviews were conducted with the boys. The boys were placed in groups of three with the exception of one which had a pair because of the COVID crisis. The boys were placed in groups according to their grades and with individuals with whom they were familiar. This provided a less intense environment when compared to individual interviews (Then, Ali & Ranking, 2014). This comfort space allowed for the free flow of expressions as well as interactions among the boys. As I listened to their expressions and observed their interactions in response to my questions, new surprising revelations surfaced, which deepened my understanding of the topic (Then et al., 2014).

Ethical Considerations

As qualitative researchers embark on gathering data, the methods employed in doing so must be underpinned by ethical principles (Creswell, 2008).

The first principle is acquiring permission from the relevant authorities to enter and access the sites (Baines, Taylor & Vanclay, 2013). Hence, I personally visited the sites and requested permission from the principals to access the sites,

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

interview participants, observe remedial literacy classes and to gain access to the grade four literacy records. Upon receiving verbal permission, I revisited the sites with official letters for the principals. Upon receiving permission, I inquired of the literacy specialist(s) and class teachers who prepared students for external examinations. When recommendations were provided, I moved on to acquire permission from the participants.

Two essential principles guiding research are confidentiality and the notion of informed consent (Baines et al.,2013). I personally approached the two literacy specialists and the two class teachers to verbally request their permission to use them as participants in my research. I explained to them that the data gathered would be for the purpose of my research only. I also explained that to gather data, I would observe them while in practice and make written records and then engage them in audio taped interviews at their convenience, for 30 to 60 minutes at each siting. I made it clear that the audio taping was for the sole purpose of ensuring that the data was accurately captured. I reassured them of confidentiality and privacy of data disseminated. Further, I explained that pseudonyms would be used to refer to them and the school. I assured them that their participation was voluntary and as such they could withdraw from the process at any given time. Upon receiving such permission, I formulated written consent forms outlining the purpose and nature of the study, their role in the research process and reassured them of confidentiality and privacy. I began the data collection process after all written consent forms were signed and returned.

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

Also, since official school documents were to be analyzed, I reassured the principals that confidentiality would be maintained and that pseudonyms would be used for the research. I also made it clear that sensitive student data would not be leaked and that I would not photocopy or take pictures of the raw data, but would use a book to manually record the data.

Further, since minors were participants in the research, I requested permission from the principals for them to be participants. I assured the principals that no emotional and physical harm would come to them. Then, under the oversight of the principals, verbal permission was sought from the male student participants. As I had previously done with the teacher participants, I explained using simple terms the purpose and nature of the research, that confidentiality and privacy would be upheld and that they would not be forced into participating. Consent forms were then sent to parents outlining the nature and purpose of the research. Confidentiality and privacy were also guaranteed.

Finally, the schools as well as students were assigned pseudonyms. I named the schools Castle Bridge and Matthew Hall Primary. The teachers from Castle Hall Primary were referred to as Mrs. Beans and Mrs. Brown. The grade four boys interviewed were assigned the names Roy and Samuel. The teachers from Matthew Hall Primary were assigned the names Mrs. Blacks and Mrs. Johns. The grade six boys were referred to as Rodger, Christi and Shenko. Finally, the grade four boys were assigned the following names: Irvine, Prince and Rev.

Reliability and Validity

Qualitative research is highly subjective. As such, the findings are more open to be questioned. It is therefore critical to take steps to ensure reliability and validity of data collected and analyzed. This will ensure that the findings are credible and consistent (Creswell, 2008). In order to ensure the reliability and validity of the data, I used triangulation, peer debriefing and member checking.

In relation to triangulation, Alexander (2001) as cited by Rahman and Yeasmin (2012) notes that the purpose of triangulation is to “obtain confirmation of findings through convergence of different perspectives. The point at which the perspectives converge is seen to represent reality” (p.154). Benefit of triangulation outlined is that it helps “researchers can hope to overcome the weakness or intrinsic biases and the problems that come from single-method, single-observer, single-theory studies” (p.154). During this research I employed a trilateral approach to ensure accuracy of data collected and to mitigate bias. These included interviews, observations and tape recordings.

The “second lens [employed] for establishing validity” (Creswell & Miller, 2000, p.125) was that of member checking. Curtin and Fossey (2007) outline that member checking is a “way of finding out whether the data analysis is congruent with the participants’ experiences” (p.9). As such, the participants were allowed during and after the research process to cross check and verbally verify the data and the findings. To facilitate this, during several point of the all interviews, I would use the echo method to verify if my understanding of their perspectives was accurate. Further, I sent the audio recording as well as the

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

transcriptions of the interviews to the teacher participants. Later, I sent the themes and overall findings via email to ascertain if my findings were in line with their positions.

The final method of triangulation used was peer debriefing. According to Lincoln and Guba (1985), peer debriefing is the use of someone familiar with the phenomenon under consideration to offer constructive criticism on matters as the researcher's assumption, research methods and interpretations. As such, I asked a more knowledgeable peer who had engaged in a similar research to examine two of the transcripts with my codes and analytical memos and to provide critical feedback on my initial findings. Later, after I had identified my themes and completed the process of organizing that aspect of the research, I again engaged this peer to analyze them in line with the discussed transcripts.

Data Analysis

Collecting the data for a qualitative research is the preliminary aspect of the research process. The data must then be prepared, managed, analyzed and interpreted. The first step in the process was preparing and organizing the data. This was done by creating a folder for the research data. The observational field notes, audio recordings of interviews, transcripts and typed raw statistical data from school documents were placed in the folder and labeled according to the site and file content. The folder was saved on a thumb-drive specifically for the research and then forwarded to my emails.

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

The next step was to properly format the observational field notes and transcripts. I read through the observational field notes and transcripts to ensure that the information was complete, legible and accurate. I then examined all data sources and anonymized names of participants, myself, data collection site, date and time. This will be followed by using Microsoft word to double space the documents, number the lines, and create wide margins.

Next, after the data was properly formatted I mused through the data to get a sense of the direction of the research. I penned visual concept maps to make initial connections. After this was done I engaged in a more diligent inquiry of the data with the research questions in mind. This was done to ensure that as I embarked on examining the raw data, it would be approached in a deliberate and focused manner. This was important as volumes of data was collected from the research sites.

After reviewing my research questions, I listened intently to the fifteen audio tapes of the interviews. This was followed by carefully reading through each document several times so as to become intimately acquainted with the data in terms of perspectives, feelings and ideas emanating from the participants. I penned my preliminary thoughts and mapped these with my initial assumptions. I also shared my initial interpretations with the teacher participants to see if these aligned to their perspectives. I then did not physically engage with the data for a few days, but used the time to mentally 'pore over' the information.

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

Next, I began the in-depth process of data analysis. I meticulously read each document, making jotted notes or memos on the wide margins as to my thoughts, reflections and questions, for more analytical consideration later on. I simultaneously revisited the observational notes to remind myself of questions and comments and connected these with the memos. I used my raw notes from the Grade 4 and GSAT data and tried to make connections to my findings from the observations and transcripts. I added these to the initial memos. I paid careful attention to disparities and commonalties within and between the documents and made notations for further probing. I made connections with the research questions to identify emerging concepts. Where connections are made, I placed special markers which were coded, to indicate which connects to each of my three questions. Red markers were assigned to surprising new concepts, so as to revisit them later.

The next step was categorizing the data (Leedy & Ormrod, 2010). This meant coding of the data from the previous step. This was done manually. All documents (interviews and observations) were reexamined and recurring patterns related to the research questions colour coded. Codes were formulated to describe these portions of the data using two methods. I used emic codes or those used by the interviewed participants, as well as etic codes, those which will be formulated by myself. All codes were typed using bold letters and colour coded in relation to the research questions. This will be done for easy identification. The documents were revisited with the focus on emerging 'surprises' and their connection to the research questions. Where connections were had, these were coded.

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

All the codes were typed on a separate page. The source documents were revisited to ensure that the codes accurately captured the essence of the documents. Additional codes were added, while redundant codes were deleted or collapsed under better suited ones. During this process, the memos were simultaneously revisited and modified in line with emerging data. To ensure rigor, I then engaged a peer to offer constructive criticism on my approach to this process as well as findings.

The next process was to group the codes into similar categories or clusters. Each category was then named. The next step was to interpret the data. Six themes were then formulated from these categories. These were: boys literacy underachievement, boys' perceptions, boys' limited literacy engagement, the nature /nurture influence, parental aptitudes and attitudes and teacher practice. I then formulated assertions from these themes. I shared these with the teacher participants to ensure that the themes represented their perspectives on the topic. Finally, I made connections with the literature to see if themes emerging validated, contradicted or unearthed new discoveries on the research.

Chapter 4

Introduction

In this chapter, I provide a discussion of the findings which emerged from the data analyzed. This chapter is organized in sections. First, the research question is highlighted. Next, the themes and or sub-themes connected to the research question are presented. An overview of each theme and or sub-theme is provided before the discussion. The data derived from each school is presented in a comparative and contrastive manner to highlight areas of similarity and variance in line with the themes and or sub-themes. Statistical data is also interspersed among findings, for the purpose of measuring their validity.

Overview of findings

The findings presented in this section of the paper embodies the experiences and perceptions shared by participants as well as those emerging from observations and analysis of school documents. Such findings finger a multiplicity of complex and interwoven factors impacting boys' literacy achievement. These factors are represented in several themes as Boys Literacy Underachievement, Boys' Negative Attitudes, Boys' Perceptions, the Nature /Nurture Influence, Parental Aptitudes and Attitudes and Teacher Practice.

Research Question 1.**What are the perspectives of teachers on the literacy achievement a group of boys at two rural primary schools?****Theme: Boys' Literacy Underachievement**

All the participants voiced the idea that boys in general were lagging behind in literacy in relation to girls. Also, it was their opinion that writing was an area of boys' performance which is at the crisis level as many are handicapped by weak writing skills.

Mrs. Johns spoke to boys' literacy underachievement as a pattern which extends "up to grade six". She added that her classes were "male dominated" with a ratio of "three to one". For her, boys lack literacy "foundation" as they have challenges "with letter sounds, writing their names and identifying the alphabet." She then pointed to an extreme crisis in writing in recent times as "it is the worse [she] have seen it." For Mrs. Johns, boys writing performance stands in sharp contrast to their performance in other academic areas where the "grades [are] good"

Mrs. Blacks agreed with Mrs. Johns adding that "for the writing they enter at a lower level than the reading". In relation to reading and writing, she explained that they:

struggle with pronouncing words with multiple syllables, [are] unable to draw inferences ... conclusions" and "with some being "unable to use context clues while they're reading". They are "unable to organize their thoughts... sequence ... use transitional words... [use] compound and complex sentences... and age appropriate vocabulary

Mrs. Small, too noted a deterioration in the writing performance of her classes. She highlighted that “writing activit[ies] are limited to a paragraph... lack cohesion and the grammar very bad.

While the literature addressing boys writing challenges is sparse, much has been documented as to boys’ aversion to writing. For example, Scott (2012) posits that for many boys, the word writing’ is synonymous with solitary confinement. Further, according to Daley (1979) many suffer from writing apprehension and as such generally go to great lengths to circumvent or delay engagement in the activity.

Further, boys’ pattern of literacy underachievement in general finds support with some bodies of literature. For example, Coles and Hall (2002) along with Jones and Myhill (2004) point to boys’ literacy underachievement dating as far back as the 17th century. Within the global and local contexts context too, documented research suggests a worsening trend in boys’ reading and writing achievement in relation to girls (Booth & Elliot –Brown,2009; Clarke,2012; Scott,2012). This pattern of literacy underachievement has resulted in the descriptors ‘struggling’ as well as ‘struggling reader’ often being ascribed to boys (Lewis,2010).

I carefully examined the statistical data from the grade four literacy test to see if they contradicted or corroborated with the literature and the expressions of the participants. The data for the larger site, Castle Bridge Primary spanned six

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

years', from 2014 to 2019. The data examined reflected the performance of 795 students for that period. Of this number, 418 were females and 377 were males. Of this six years, 2014 to 2018 represented the grade four literacy test, while for 2019, the grade four Language Arts PEP. For Matthew Hall primary, ten years of data from 2009-2018 was collected as this site is considerably smaller in student population. The data reflected the performance of 151 students. Of this number, 80 were males. The data was analyzed based on two areas: gender and overall performance.

When the data were analyzed as a whole, boys seemed to be underperforming in comparison to girls. For example, For Castle Bridge Primary, 26% of boys attained mastery while 23% did not. On the other hand, there was a wider gap present with girls, as 41% of displayed mastered while 10% did not (*see Figure 1.1*). For the smaller research site, Matthew Hall primary, 26 % of boys displayed mastery as opposed to 40% of girls. However, an equal number of boys 26 % did not attain mastery. In contrast, only 8% of girls fell in that category (See Figure 1.2). Hence, through comparative analysis boys were found to be lagging behind.

Figure 1. 1. This figure shows the overall percentile performance for both sexes at Castle Bridge Primary for 2014-2019

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

Figure 1. 2 . This figure shows the overall percentile performance for both sexes at Matthew Hall Primary for 2009-2018

However, when the statistical data was analyzed in relation to performance within gender, the performance of boys as a group, was not as dismal as posited in the literature and the interviews. Analysis of performance of males across the sites shows the majority of boys (as a group) attaining mastery, but by a slim margin. For example, For Castle Bridge Primary, 58% of boys attained mastery while 42% did not (see figure.2). For Matthew Hall primary, the data revealed that an equal number of boys or 50% had either attained or not attained mastery (See figure 2.2). While the performance of boys is not at a comfort level, the statistical data does seem to support the idea that boys' literacy performance as a group is at the crisis level.

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

Figure 2. 1. This figure shows Castle Bridge Primary Percentile 'within Gender' Performance for Boys (2014-2019)

Figure 2. 2. This figure shows Matthew Hall Primary 'Within Gender' Performance for Boys (2009-2018)

Bodies of literature have risen to support the idea that boys' literacy performance is a far cry from a crisis. For example, Alloway (2007), Berrill and Martino (2003) suggest that to categorize boys' literacy performance as a crisis is an exaggeration of the facts. They contend that deep analysis of the data reveals that many boys are achieving in reading and writing.

Research Questions 2**How do teachers describe their experiences in developing the reading and writing skills of boys at two rural primary school?****Theme: Boys' Negative Attitude**

It was the view of the participants that the perceptions and negative attitudes of boys towards literacy had resulted in limited engagement in school based as well as independent reading and writing. Such negative attitudes and perceptions makes it a challenge for these participants to productively engage boys in literacy activities.

I had noted that the room occupied by Mrs. Beans was quite print rich. I inquired if boys would venture to the reading areas. She responded that only “one percent of the entire population of boys would” with “half of that number looking at the pictures”. Mrs. Blacks who too has several reading stations in her classroom echoed similar sentiments. In relation to writing, she noted: “my boys don’t write independently. Even for school based writing, boys who are avid readers, have to be nudged to write.”

Supporting the stance of the teacher participants is Hyatt’s (2002) who posits that many boys have a negative attitude towards school based writing and are reluctant writers. Millard (2002) postulates that even competent writers dislike most school-based writing. It is this abhorrence for writing which directly influences their levels of independent writing engagements (Meuriso –Storm ,2006; Hyatt, 2002). As it relates to reading, Clarke (2012) finds that some boys

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

do not value reading as an activity and as such do not seek out opportunities for reading. This has a direct bearing on their reading achievement.

Theme: The Nurture/ Nature Influence

For the participants, these two theories are complexly interwoven allies in boys' literacy underachievement. They have a direct bearing on boys' levels of literacy engagement and literacy achievement.

For Mrs. Beans, the social construct of masculinity is fueling the underachievement of boys in reading and writing. For her, individuals within society had been psychologically conditioned to acquiesce to the nurture ideology:

So, I think that the society, the culture [has] a lot do with our development.... The way we think, the way we train our minds... It is our minds that we are going to use to produce this reading and writing. If our minds have conditions contrary to what is required for reading and writing, then we will not read and write.

She added:

We're creatures that learn from our environment and adapt to our environment. As such children learn what they are supposed to do [and] not supposed to do... boys learn that they are ...and not to complain and ... talk about problems. It is this kind of culture is [which is] impacting boys today in how they learn and what they learn...

For Mrs. Beans this has unwittingly nurtured a culture in favour of females. She explained that when there are challenges with girls:

Mommy and aunty come in and say, 'what is happening? Talk to me about it'. It's not the same response for boys generally ... They tend to feel like they cannot talk to anybody about it, so when they bottle up all of that emotion and when they become overwhelmed, it's going to burst out.

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

For this participant “suppression of thoughts” has deep implications for boys’ emotional state, which has a domino effect on literacy achievement. She recounted “... [Their] little brain[s] cannot deal with all of that plus school. [it] impact them... it impacts reading and writing.” For her, complicating this situation is the biological makeup of the sexes. She noted “it’s a biological thing”, “girls are more adoptive... than males and they figure it out. But boys tend to internalize and it impacts reading and writing in a great way”

Mrs. Blacks added that social conditioning had infiltrated the homes of boys, inflicting blows to boy’s literacy engagement. She stated that it’s a “cultural thing that reading for the females [and] emphasis is not placed on getting the boys to read.” She added: “parents ensure that the girls have to take up their books while the boys are able to go on the road and enjoy themselves.”

For Mrs. Johns, boys have bought into the culturally defined idea of masculinity. This has impacted their writing development as they actively resist writing about topics which are perceived as feminine. She noted “there are certain topics that the boys don’t want to discuss. They’ll tell you that those are girl topics.”

Bodies of literature support the expressions of the participants. For example, Abdullah and Mohd-Asraf, 2016, and Scott,2012, posits that boys will naturally steer away from literacy activities as they are psychologically conditioned to believe that engaging in such activities will strip them of their masculinity. Also, while Dutro (2001) challenges the idea that reading is a

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

gendered activity the idea is advanced that boys perceive certain kinds of texts as gender specific, as boy and girl books. Such perceptions are well guarded and boundaries are never crossed.

Mrs. Brown is of the view that boys' biological wiring stalls their literacy development. She related that "cognitively boys in general do not learn concept as early as girls and that their writing usually develops a little later than girls." Mrs. Brown concluded by positing her belief that the plain would eventually be leveled in favour of boys:

These same boys will go on ...[and] when I saw them, they're like, 'miss you remember me? So, how you doing now? They are showing me that they have come a long way and that's fine. They are making something of themselves, so later on.

Mrs. Blacks agrees that biological factors do influence levels of boys' literacy engagement. In discussion with her she noted that boys: "don't like to write a lot" it's a "biological thing", as they like to "solve problems quickly". She then added that it was her experience that boys are naturally "more verbal". She noted that she always had active protest from boys who would ask "miss why we have to write all of that in so many words?" She then related an instance where she had asked a group to write a story about a ship wreck. One young man raised his hands and with knitted brows asked "then miss if di ship already wreck, what am I supposed to write?"

However, she is of the view that assenting to the idea that boys are naturally hardwired to underachieve in literacy at the primary level is fatal to their literacy development. She related that within her context, this has created a

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

situation where teachers fail to adjust their pedagogical approach to address boys' literacy deficiencies, as they "leave it up to time", on the premise that "boys will catch up." For Mrs. Blacks challenging this ideology is the best path towards improving boys' literacy achievement.

The concept that boys are innately underachievers in literacy and that there will be a narrowing of the gap as boys mature is pillared by bodies of literature as Biddulph (2008). However, this school of thought has been classified as absurd and baseless, as it lacks imperial evidence. First, evidence points to an unabated widening of the literacy gap. Also, neurological research reveal that the brain is malleably and not hard-wired. This is demonstrated by the fact that many boys defy the theory by being successful readers and writers at the primary level (Lynn & Mikk ,2009; Kaiser et al.,2009). Moreover, Whitehead (2011) contends that this theory is dangerous for boys' literacy development as teachers who rely on it perpetuate the idea that boys are underachiever by failing to address their literacy needs. It is their inaction which stagnates the literacy growth of such boys and widens the literacy gap.

Theme: Parental Aptitude and Attitudes

It was the unanimous position of the teacher participants that the parents' attitude, be it negative or positive, has a direct bearing boys' literacy performance. For them, boys take a cue from the attitudes of parents and replicate these in their own attitudes towards reading and writing. The participants also voiced the idea

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

that many parents do not understand their role in the literacy development of their children and thus all is left to the teacher.

Mrs. Blacks highlighted the direct link between parental support and boys' literacy achievement. She related that she had a "class once, 10 boys and 2 girls" where there "was lot of support from the parents". The result was that there was no "boy that was reading below the grade 6 level."

According to Mrs. Beans parental attitudes is reflected in how print rich homes are. She said "home involvement is critical to reading and writing" as "we're creatures that learn from [and] adapt to our environment." Mrs. Johns and Mrs. Blacks also spoke to their experiences. Mrs. Blacks said that "...parents do not provide the children with a lot of reading materials at home." Mrs. Johns recounted:

They don't take them out. They don't provide them with the vicarious experience either. They are not exposed to the kinds of experiences which supports good writing.

Low levels of parental involvement were also credited as a deterrent to boys' literacy achievement. Mrs. Blacks offered several perspectives in this regards. First, parental aptitude or literacy level determined the extent of parental involvement. She noted that because some "parents themselves are unable to read ...they're unable to assist their boys effectively."

Another insight provided by Mrs. Blacks is that parents lack an understanding of their role in their children's literacy development. She highlighted that most "parents leave it upon the teachers" as they "don't see that they have a role when it comes to assisting their children."

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

A final perspective offered is parents' lack of interest. Boys feed on what is communicated through such negative attitudes, namely that reading is not essential. Mrs. Blacks recounted that "if the parents are not putting much interest, [the] children [will not] know that they are to pay much attention to reading." Mrs. Beans affirmed this stance and related that the difference between those boys who were literacy competent and those who were not, lie with the extent to which "their parents were interested". For her group, lack of parental interest has deprived the boys of the needed support to thrive. For her, the sessions allocated for literacy is "not enough to provide the kind of ground work that is needed". Hence follow-up by parents is critical. But this is lacking. She added that her efforts to engage parents in a partnership has been met by a familiar road block: a nonchalant attitude. This was made explicit in a message sent by a parent: "mumi se, shi no hab no taim. Shi kyaahn kom, di tiicha loki, di tiicha no hab eniting fi du?"

Various bodies of literature corroborate the aforementioned position of the teacher participants. According to Stanovich (1986) low levels of parental support widens the literacy gap between achievers and non-achievers, as the absence of the parent element stagnates literacy development. Other bodies of literature posit that parental involvement is determined by their level of self-efficacy. When parents' levels of literacy are low they tend to shy away from active involvement in their children's literacy development, while the converse is true of parents with high levels of literacy (Ice & Hoover-Dempsey, 2010; Nehal, 2017).

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

Further Hoover-Dempsey and Sandler (1997) emphasize that parents' beliefs and perception of their role in their children's literacy development are high determinants of levels of involvement. Parents are more likely to actively support and guide the literacy development of their children if they perceived their role as critical in this regard. Nehal (2017) adds that that parents' attitudes dictated by their belief systems as well as perceptions of their roles will either fuel or asphyxiate their children's literacy progress.

Research Question 3 **How do Boys Perceive their Literacy Achievement?**

Theme: Boys' Perceptions

As I interrogated the data, two intriguing findings emerged. First, boys perceive themselves as less successful readers and writers. Second, boys do see reading and writing as important activities, but only as it relates to academic advancement. As a result, they do not see the need to engage in these activities for pleasure.

An interesting idea surfaced from seven of the eight participants during the interviews. It was their perception that girls are higher achievers in reading and writing. This perspective finds support with Clarke (2016). Two attributed this is the extended time spent in engaging in these activities. Shenko said: "... dem always a read". Christi then highlighted a contrast in how both genders use their time: "Ms. they stay home and read so sometime we go to our friend house. But the mother tells the girl to stay inside." These combined expressions suggest that

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

parents unwittingly or purposefully communicate that reading and writing are feminine activities and as such boys are allowed to use their time to indulge in recreational activities. This conclusion is also supported by Edwards and Jones (2018) and Scott (2012).

As I engaged in discussion with the boys, it was the voiced consensus that they saw reading and writing as important, but only within the context of career advancement. Rev said: Ms. reading is important, you will get nuff things, you will have your education. Irvin added: You have to read ... if you want to be a doctor....” Shenko pointed out that writing skills are important to excel in external examinations. He related: “because when you go into PEP you already know what to do.” Much of the literature point to boys’ natural abhorrence to reading and writing (Meuriso –Storm ,2006; Hyatt, 2002). However, the aforementioned expressions of the boys contradict this argument as boys perceive writing to be important, but only within the context of school.

When I asked the question: Are you a member of a library? The response was in the affirmative for most of the male participants from Matthew Hall Primary. When I asked them how often they visited the school library in a week, Christie was one of the first to voice his experience. His response was “once”. I then asked him if he read outside of school. His response was in the affirmative. I followed with the question: For how long do you read? His response indicated short stints. He said “Ms. for like 10 [minutes]. Another grade six participant Shenko admitted

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

that he infrequently visited the library to read. His response was that he visited the library “one time” in a month.

I also inquired from the grade four boys if they engaged in literacy activities outside school. One of the participant, Irvine, stated that he did no writing outside of class. When asked for what purpose he used his gadgets at home, his immediate response was “Go on Google... watch shows and videos”. Another student, Prince, said that he used his gadget for other activities, with reading with reading being mentioned last on the list: “play game and play games and watch videos, read stories.” It has been postulated by Atkinson (2009) and Blair and Sanford (2004) that boys who display an aversion for in- school literacy often engaged in literacy practices outside of school. However, expressions from the participants contradict this argument as most indicate limited engagement in reading and writing outside of school. This finds support with the research of Musza (2016) and Clarke (2012) who posit that many boys do not seek out opportunities for engagement in independent literacy activities, but opt instead to engage in recreational activities.

Research Question 4**What has been the Experiences of Boys with their Reading and Writing Development?****Theme: Teacher Practice**

The findings reveal that boys' literacy experiences are directly tied to teacher practice. Teacher practice was found to be determined by perceptions, attitudes, knowledge and pedagogical competence.

Sub-Theme: Perceptions of and Approaches to Assessment

Findings from interviews and observation of participants revealed contrasting perspectives on assessment and its role in literacy development.

For Mrs. Brown, literacy assessment is synonymous with structured tests. It functions as an identifier of students' reading levels or for the purpose of assigning grades. She related that students are "assessed every September" with "pre-tests" and "whole tests are administered at the end of the year". She added that she does assessments to "know their levels". However, such assessments are done "in a group setting because the test can be very long...[to] do individually."

Another participant, Mrs. Black expressed the view that within her context many teachers as well as the administration have framed assessment through narrow lens. For them, assessment is synonymous with test. For this participant, such tests are mere snapshots of students' performance and not necessarily true reflections of their weakness and proficient levels.

She reported:

Within our school I don't think we using assessment properly or we're using the data that we get from assessment to drive the teacher and learning process, because I don't think that one test at the end of the school year or at the end of the term can really assess the students' mastery level or their proficiency level.

Mrs. Blacks voiced the idea that there was a lack of understanding on the part of schools on the link between assessment and boys' literacy development and experience. She then made reference to the management of the grade four literacy data. She related that for the school, "the information is just left at the office ...it is analyzed and it is kept there. She noted the administration does not "have meetings to say this is what has happened with our students and how can fix it, what are the best practices that we can use to address these challenges." She then added that she operates in a context where teachers take a cue from the administration's position on assessment, noting that she did not "think the teachers see it necessary to analyze the data ... because administration is not really pushing."

For her however, her perception and approach to assessment has reaped a pattern of success in boys' literacy performance. In discussion she outlined that she gathered data through teacher conferencing. She stated that when she gets a class the "first thing [she] does is to speak to the teacher". She also uses summative data as she "goes back to the grade four results and get a better idea of the strength and weakness ... so [as to] plan accordingly". She uses

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

“continuous assessment to guide [her] in developing lessons to assist the students and in providing differentiated instructions”.

The literature supports the idea that for many educators the concept assessment is synonymous with test. It noted that there are low levels of assessment literacy among many educators. Hence many cannot effectively use it effectively drive reading and writing development. While one participant lays the blame at the feet of school administration, the literature deepens the discussion, and goes to the root of the problem: teacher training institutions which have failed dismally to train teachers to understand and employ literacy assessment effectively (Popham, 2004; Wongwanich & Yantim 2013).

Sub-Theme: Teacher focus: Students Needs or the Curriculum?

Findings from the data indicate that for the participants, meeting the demands of the curriculum while addressing the needs of students has proven to be an arduous task. The pressure to produce results for high stake exams which determines a school’s ranking, forces some participants to make the ultimate sacrifice.

For Mrs. Brown the ultimate sacrifice has been her students –the majority of which are boys. Though she admitted that this present approach is counterproductive and it never makes students “ready for exams”, she feels pressured to pursue it none-the-less. She attributes this to a school ‘structure’ which dictates an exam driven position.

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

She exclaimed:

[The] curriculum determines what they should be doing.... Do you understand? There's a particular structure here... So, you can't say okay the children can't manage this amount of content.... you cannot wait until you see the children comfortable right here. You just have to keep the pace with the curriculum.

She then admitted that this route is “frustrating as the time you finish a lesson they are exhausted, you are exhausted. It's like, it's too much”. She then noted that the high levels of frustration have resulted in unrelenting resistance from the boys who are “fighting back” as it is “above their levels”. They cannot “connect “with the content and hence don’t not “see the relevance of it”.

In an interview with the male students of the class, several findings surfaced. Foremost, was the boys’ high level of frustration which had an emotional toll on them. For them, this stirred them away from school based literacy engagement. In response to the question about what reading and writing classes are like, Samuel who reads at the grade one level said: “Mis, som a di taim mi no nuo wa fi du bot mi chrii an dwiit Mis kaaz som a dem riili haad”. With eyes brimming with tears said: Mi no riid wen mi ankomfatebl....das wai mi no laik riid a skuul mis ,kaaz shi lov gi wi haad tingz fi riid..... mi riid wen mi go huom out a mi uona bok dem.” He then voiced the emotional scarring from inability to keep pace :“Mi fiil bad kaaz mi a riid an mi no nuo ow fi riid it...Mi fiil sad”... “Mis som a di taim mi wish mi go iina waahn ada klaas”.

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

When I asked him to describe what made him uncomfortable in writing sessions, he said:

Shi rosh it thruu Mis .Yu si wen wi a rait weh shi se wi fi ed op, az won minit don an niivn don ed op shi waahn wi fi stap ... shi jos wah rosh di work fi we dwiit... wen shi a put work pan di buod shi no tek taim, shi jos a rait it faas an a rait a go dong. Wi tel aar seh if shi kyaahn stap til we rich de dier. shi se no. shi til a rait

When asked what they would do to improve reading and writing classes, the overwhelming response was making the lessons at their pace with teacher feedback and support. Roy said: “miss I would say you all are finish writing? And then if all of dem se yes miss I go on with the work.”

Samuel then added:

Yes, mis an wen if wi doont get dem rait shi eksplien it to wi an mek wi chrai get dem rait... Mi wudn gi dem no haad work. Mi wuda si dong wid dem an help dem riid

While there is a dearth of literature on the impact of high stake exams on the literacy experiences of boys, one spoke to its debilitating impact on children’s’ literacy development. This literature supports the experience of Mrs. Browns’ male students. For example, Darwish (2016) stress that preparation for high stake examinations and covering the curriculum are high on the agenda of many school administrations. As such, much pressure is mounted on teachers to conform to the dictated culture. This is detrimental to writing development as the teachers’ pedagogy is aligned to the schools’ agenda instead of students’ writing needs.

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

Another important concept emerging from the interviews is the need for lessons to reflect the interests and preferences of boys. In discussion with them they revealed their fixation with what they termed “boy books”. For them this meant scientific and cultural materials with pictures and few words. They also had a fixation with art and drawing. When asked if their interests in art and certain books are reflected in class lessons, Roy said: “no mis shi no laik wen wi du aart work.”

I then asked him what he would write about if he was given a choice. His response was: “Miss I will ask dem to write about an animal.” Samuel added: “mek dem jraa shaak an tingz mis. An deb di gorl dem kan jraa dali, put sentens bout dem mis”. Samuel’s response reveals his perception that writing activities should be tailored to gender preferences and that this would be a good springboard for stimulating writing. For him, there is no aversion to writing, but there needs to be the right kind of stimulus.

Another important point surfacing from the interview is that the teacher reflected a bias in the kinds of material used as content. Hence, boys seeming aversion to reading seems to be linked to the materials chosen by educators. When asked if the books they enjoyed reading were used as reading materials, Samuel expressed himself this way: “Shi yuuz muor tingz fi gorl.”

In sharp contrast with Mrs. Brown, Mrs. Johns sees facilitating students’ preferences and interests as essential to driving writing engagement. In reference to boys she noted that “they get bored easily and prefers to write something interesting. I let them write about what they like.” Mrs. Blacks endorsed Mrs.

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

Johns' response adding that "boys are more interested in hands on stuff" and "that if they are [allowed to write about these], you get them in terms of the reading and even writing." So she "provides them with things of interest to them". In discussion with the grade six and grade four boys taught by these teacher participants, I asked them if their preferences were taken into consideration for reading and writing tasks. All responded in the affirmative. When I asked the grade six boys if they liked writing, two said yes, while the other said sometimes. Rodger said that he "liked writing more than drawing"

The experiences of the student participants and the aforementioned teacher participants echo the arguments postulated by the literature. According to the literature, boys steer away from reading and writing as they are demotivated. (Mead ,2012; McGeown et al.,2015). According to Hughes- Hassel et al (2010) and Landt (2013) an essential motivational factor for boys is to allow them be to be engaged with books which reflect their reading preferences and which allows them to make personal connections. Such personal connections are essential to peaking and sustaining interest levels in reading. Further, Dutro (2006) as cited by Scott (2012) voiced the need for boys to be allowed to write about things that are important to them so that their writing experience can be more meaningful. Failure to do so, as exemplified by the experiences of the male student participants taught by Mrs. Brown, has resulted in a silencing of their voices, thus robbing them of active participation in literacy activities (Emig,1977; Pearl, 1980).

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

I contrasted the approach taken by Mrs. Brown to Mrs. Johns as it relates the response of each to the pressure of high stake exams to see the impact on boys' experiences with reading and writing. Mrs. Blacks who has been the only grade six teacher since 2012, has taught male dominated classes. she presented a multiplicity of literacy challenges. She stated that many of her boys she has taught struggle as they are "handicapped by a lack of foundation in writing and reading". For her present group, the boys entered "reading at grades 1 to 3 level." For her, it is "difficult to balance" because of the "pressure to perform" and get to "passes for the sort after schools." She noted that the curriculum is quite compact and requires "high levels of critical thinking skills." She sees trying to build on a non-existent foundation as tantamount to embarking on a suicide mission. Her approach is to "build foundation first" by "teach[ing] based on the challenges that [she] is presented with." She highlighted that she "differentiates a lot... use their interests, make the classes fun, so they will want to learn." She also "provides much scaffolding and individual support." She further noted that only after building a foundation that she moves on to "on covering the curriculum"

I analyzed the statistical data from the 2013-2018 GSAT external examination for the taught period for Mrs. Blacks. While the value added by the grade four and grade five teachers cannot be ignored, the positive results from the data when juxtaposed with the literacy challenges this participant has to contend with, does highlight the value of a needs focused approach as opposed to a curriculum driven approach.

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

The GSAT results for the period 2013-2018 showed that 83 students sat the exam. The data revealed a 55.4% male dominated cohort. For this period, 82% of the male cohort attained over 50% in both Language Arts and Communication Task. A deeper analysis of this data on a yearly basis revealed that for 2013, 80% achieved mastery in both Communication Task and Language Arts. For 2014, while 33% achieved above 50% in Language Arts, 100% attained 50% and above in the Communication Task (See figure 3.1). The percentages for 2015 to 2018 were 100%, 86%, 61% and 100% respectively (See figure 3.2).

Figure 3. 1. Figure shows Matthew Hall Primary's GSAT Performance for Boys (2013-2015)

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

Figure 3.2. Figure shows Matthew Hall Primary's GSAT Performance for Boys (2016-2018)

Sub-Theme: Teachers' Understanding of literacy and Levels of Digital Competence

One finding which surfaced from analyzing the voiced expressions of most participants is the intricate connection between teachers' understanding of literacy, their ability to effectively integrate technology and boys' literacy performance.

For one participant, Mrs. Brown, technology was not featured in her definition of literacy. She defined it as the "ability recognize print, interpret what is there, make the connection with it and be able to reproduce it creatively on your own." When asked about the infusion of technology in her lessons, her response indicated that she saw it as a distraction her lesson could do without. She noted that with the use of technology "which the boys could have related [to]... they got "all excited" but that is where it ended. She noted that "she realized that they failed to "pay attention to ... what [she] want[ed] them to learn." Roy confirmed

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

the limited use of technology noting that “a one-time shi carry it, one time.” Samuel in a disappointed tone added: “Yes, miss fram dat we neva use back none!” Both nodded in agreement that the lesson was fun.

One factor which could be responsible for Mrs. Brown’s lack of enthusiasm to use technology is the lack of support through training. Mrs. Beans who is a colleague of Mrs. Brown was asked about training to support the infusion of technology to support literacy development. Her response was that they had received only “technical support”.

For Mrs. Blacks, technology infusion is an absolute essential for boys’ literacy engagement. For her, boys find technology ‘natural’ and hence by using it she is able to “build on their writing.” She noted that since technology is “second nature to them, it lessens writing inhibitions” and gives them “confidence to write.” Thus, “to effectively enrich the reading and writing of these students [she] takes technology [to her] classroom by download[ing] videos.”

For the lessons observed for Mrs. Blacks, technology was seamlessly integrated and it provided a rich literacy experience for all students, but especially the boys. As soon as the smart television was brought into the room, the students were observed positioning their chairs in front of it. This indicated that technology integration was the hallmark of lessons. The aim of the lesson was to provide the students with a vicarious experience while developing their reading and writing skills. For the lesson the participant focused on a passage entitled ‘A trip to Disney land’. As the passage progressed the students were introduced to special train which transported patrons to the amusement park. No one had even

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

seen that train before and neither had any one of them traveled on a train. Mrs. Blacks used her smartphone to show them photos. Then, nearing the culmination of the lesson, the students were shown a video downloaded from YouTube which presented a blogger's experience at Disney land. The classroom was then transformed into an amusement park with the desk and chairs as the rides. At the end of this activity the students were given a composition to write on their imaginary trip to Disney Land. Although the boys wrote much less than the girls initially, all completed the task. With additional support, their pieces improved in the next class.

One common barrier highlighted by the literature to boy's literacy progress is a lack of understanding of and recognition of 21st century literacy by practitioners. Further, the lack of training for practioners in infusing technology with literacy practices has impaired their ability to develop boys' literacy. Learners today are described as 'digital natives' because of their affinity to technology. In the context of the 21st century, failure to engage boys in 21st century literacy practices which are technologically dependent, deprives them of active literacy engagement as well as the development of 21st century skills (Alloway ,2007; Kivunja,2014; Picton, 2019; Scardamalia et al., 2010).

Sub-Theme: Teaching Writing: Perceptions, Attitudes and Competence

Some participants agreed that there was an imbalance in the schools' focus as it relates to reading and writing. It was the general consensus that there was an over focus on reading, with wide-scale neglect of writing. This neglect has had an inimical effect on boys' attitude towards writing. For two participants, two major factors are linked to this imbalance: teacher attitude and competence level.

For Mrs. Blacks and Mrs. Johns limited focus on writing by teachers have been an area of disquiet. Mrs. Johns noted that she had "been complaining over the years that they need to concentrate on writing as they don't spend much time teaching them at the lower levels." Mrs. Blacks also expressed similar sentiments, adding that students' writing development is seriously impaired. She said: "when they come to grade 6 you realize most times they don't even know how to develop their topic sentence and the supporting sentences"

Mrs. Blacks described composition as a highly cognitive process which "is unnatural and has to be taught. She noted that many teachers "do not understand the writing process". She fingered the school administration's failure to prioritize writing as a cause for the demise of writing. It was her perception that teachers had taken a cue from the lapse attitude of the school administration. She recounted "...everybody does their own things. Administration doesn't call workshop for reading and writing. Nothing is done about the writing within the school."

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

For the majority of the participants, teacher incompetence was found to be a major contributor to the writing imbalance in these two schools. Admitting to her own deficiencies, Mrs. Johns said:” I think I feel so incompetent to address it right. It has been a while.” She then pointed to the lack of expertise in developing student literacy as a school wide problem, noting that the teachers “don’t know what to do.”

For Mrs. Beans the real culprit is the lack of effective training to teach writing. Speaking to the quality of workshops she noted that some members of the support team from the “ministry ... don't have a clue what they're doing.” Mrs. Johns too spoke about the lack of instructional support to teach writing. As Mrs. Johns sat in front of me, I could see her searching deep into her brain, trying to drag her memory. She revealed: “workshops mostly deal with reading... not writing. I’m trying to remember if I’ve been to any writing sessions.” The inadequacies of external workshops have forced her to engage in self –teaching and development via online sources. She reported: “I go on the internet, to see lessons. I do a lot of research.”

Graham and Rijlaarsdam (2016) found much deficiencies in literacy instructional practices of practioners. Their interrogation of classroom practice revealed that many teachers lack an awareness of effective approaches to facilitate and support writing competency. This results in a mismatch between learner needs and approaches employed and further alienates boys from writing.

Further, many educators lack knowledge of the connection between reading and writing. As a result, in an overemphasis on reading and under focus

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

on writing (Graham, 2019). For Graham (2008) lack of teacher support and effective training, lies at the core of the problem. These have rendered them incompetent to develop students' writing skills.

Summary

The findings reveal that boys' literacy achievement is not as dismal as is postulated by some participants and by some bodies of literature. Further, boys view reading and writing as important activities. Moreover, it was found that external forces as the perceptions, attitudes, knowledge, competence levels of parents, teachers, school administration and ministry representatives are the most powerful determinants of boys' literacy achievement.

Chapter 5

In this chapter the report summary, summary of findings, Implications, conclusions, recommendations and limitation were featured.

Report Summary

I engaged in a qualitative research on boys' literacy achievement at the primary level. To garner data for the study used two primary school as research sites which had a high concentrations boy. I interviewed and observed two classrooms teachers assigned to grades six and four as well as two literacy specialists. Eight male student participants from grade four and six taught by teacher participants were also interviewed to holistic picture of boys' literacy achievement. Summative data from external examinations were also interrogated for the purpose of validation and deeper probe into the topic. The data was collected, formatted and transcribed. Codes were identified and analytic memos created. Codes were used to formulate five themes. The literature was then contrasted and compared to the findings. Finally, conclusions, implications and recommendations were formulated in line with the findings.

Summary of Findings

Research Question 1

What are the perspectives of teachers on the literacy achievement a group of boys at two rural primary schools?

It was the perspective of most of the participants that boys are lagging behind in reading and writing in relation to girls. For them, boys' writing performance is at a crisis level. However, when summative data was contrasted with the expressions from participants on boys' literacy achievement, somewhat contradictory findings emerged. While the general statistical data found boys to be lagging behinds in comparison to girls, when the data was analyzed within gender, the majority of boys, though, by a slim margin had attained mastery in literacy. This suggests that the word 'crisis' in relation to their performance may a stretch of sorts.

Research Question 2

How do teachers describe their experiences in developing the reading and writing skills of boys at two rural primary school?

The participants voiced several factors which impacted reading and writing instruction. These included boys' negative attitudes towards literacy, the influence of nature /nurture theory and parental attitudes and aptitudes. First, it was found that parental attitudes and aptitudes or literacy levels had a direct bearing on levels of parental involvement. This in turn was mirrored in boys' literacy achievement. Also, as it relates to the nature /nurture influence, it was found that some parents and boys had bought into the social construct of masculinity. As a result, boys'

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

responded negatively to the teachers' efforts at developing their literacy skills. Participants had more favourable literacy performance from boys whose parents had challenged the theories. Also, the extent to which teachers had positive experiences with literacy instruction was also determined by the extent to which they bought into and accentuated one or both of these theories. Teachers who based their practice on one or both of these theories were met with lower literacy attainment. However, the converse was the reality for those who acknowledged but challenged them.

Research Question 3

How do boys at two primary schools perceive their literacy achievement?

It was also found that boys perceive girls as more competent in literacy. However, they do not have negative attitudes towards school based reading and writing, as they are perceived as important to career advancement. But, most do not see the connection between independent reading and writing and their literacy achievement, and so they engage in reading and writing primarily for academic purpose. It was also found that boys have certain preferences for reading and writing and the extent to which these were catered to determine their levels of literacy engagement.

Research Question 4**What has been the experiences of boys with reading and writing development?**

The findings revealed contrasting experiences of boys during reading and writing instruction. The extent to which such experiences were negative or positive and resulted in positive or negative attitudes towards schools based literacy was directly linked the teacher practice. Boys who had more positive experiences, which was reflected in improved literacy achievement, did so in environments where teachers challenged gender binaries, where pedagogy was grounded in constructivism, and where the teacher had a sound understanding of writing instruction, literacy and literacy assessment.

Conclusion

In analyzing the findings, I have arrived at the conclusion that categorizing boys as a group as underachievers and labelling their literacy achievement as a crisis is an exaggeration of the facts. This conclusion finds support in the academic with Alloway (2007), Berrill and Martino (2003) and Landt (2013) among others.

Another conclusion arrived at is that boys' literacy achievement is largely dependent on external forces beyond their control. The aptitudes, perceptions, actions, knowledge and levels of competence on the part of parents, teachers, school administrators and Ministry officials have a direct bearing on boys' literacy achievement. This conclusion is also supported by several literatures. For example, Nehal (2017) argues that levels of parental involvement can either fuel or asphyxiates their children's literacy progress. Also various bodies of literature contend that teachers' as well as school administrators' knowledge and

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

competence level as it relates to assessment, 21st century literacy and its associated skills and writing instruction dictate boys' response to literacy and inevitably their achievement (Abdullah & Mohd-Asraf, 2016; Alloway, 2007; Edwards & Jones, 2012; Mead, 2012; Peal, 1980; Scardamalia et al., 2010; Wongwanich & Yamtim, 2013). Finally, Graham (2008), Popham (2004) and Mertler (2003) speak to the weak support systems provided by training institutions and ministry officials, which has rendered teachers incompetent to effectively drive literacy development.

Implications

In analyzing the statistical data on boys' performance in literacy, a lingering question as to boys' true literacy performance emerged. An analysis of boys' performance as a group showed the majority at the mastery level, while a comparative analysis with girls indicates that some boys are facing a literacy crisis. This, therefore, has implications for a longitudinal investigation into the topic, involving a wider cross-section of schools and participants, as well as the analysis of grades four and six PEP performance within these contexts. Such a broad-based study would better reflect a more realistic picture of boys' literacy performance.

Also, the study revealed a great disparity between the approaches and results of the grade four and six teacher participants. The grade six teacher participant from Matthew Hall primary was guided by the constructivist theory, had a sound understanding of literacy, writing instruction and assessment strategies to drive

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

literacy development. The converse seemed to be the reality for, the grade four teacher from Castle Bridge primary. This wide disparity speaks to the need for a careful examination into professional training programmes which are often generic in nature, and result in an imbalance in teacher competence. There is a need for specialized ongoing professional training which identifies teachers' unique instructional needs and scaffolds them into developing the requisite knowledge, skills and competencies to positively drive literacy development

Recommendations

In view of the findings, the need for training on various levels is a key recommendation:

- ✓ This 21st century has effected changes on how literacy is defined and its associated skills. As such, teacher training institutions and the MOE must keep pace with the fluid nature of literacy to better equip and support literacy facilitator to meet the realities of 21st century learning.

- ✓ One of the findings emerging from the study was that some who represent the MOE at training sessions lack training. Hence, the MOE in collaboration with teacher training institutions, should partner to provide ongoing professional training in effective technology infusion with literacy instruction, literacy assessment, and writing instruction. Upon receipt of such training, ongoing training and support should be provided for teachers and school administration at the primary level.

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

- ✓ Since literacy extends across the curriculum, all individuals at teacher training institutions, should receive in-depth grounding in theories underpinning writing instruction as well as strategies to support it. Equipping all educators with such expertise will better anchor the literacy programmes and create the kind of environment for literacy development. Moreover, such training is extremely important in cases where parents have low levels of literacy and cannot provide the needed support for their children.

- ✓ Ongoing professional training sessions should be organized by literacy and primary school teachers, so that best practices in literacy instruction can be shared. During such training sessions, gender stereotypes and constructs should be explored and challenged.

- ✓ Teachers at the primary level must seek to cater to the reading and writing preferences of both sexes, so that they are motivated to engage in reading and writing activities.

Limitations

The study had limitations which must be highlighted. These specifically related to the impact of the corona-virus on the study. Originally, the study was to span a 6 to 8 weeks' period and should have included 3 sites and 19 participants. However, the study was conducted over a 5-week period and was reduced to 2 sites and 12 participants. These placed limitations on the extent to which the findings would be a true reflective of the Jamaican context.

References

- Abdullah, H., & Mohd-Asraf, R. (2016). Elementary schoolers' attitudes toward reading in English: How boys feel relative to girls. *English Language Teaching*, 9(6). Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.5539/elt.v9n6p134>
- Alkassim, R. S., Sulaiman, I.E., Musa, A. (2015). Comparison of convenience sampling and purposive sampling. *American Journal of Theoretical and Applied Statistics*,5(1),1-4. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencepublishinggroup.com/j/ajtas>
- Alloway, A. (2007). Swimming against the tide: Boys, literacies, and schooling: An Australian Story. *Canadian Journal of Education*,30(2) ,582-605. Retrieved from <http://www.jstor.org/stable/20466651>
- Alvi, M. (2016). *A manual for selecting sampling techniques in research*. Retrieved from <https://ideas.repec.org/f/pal595.html>
- Ambe, E. (2013) Developing successful writing teachers: Outcomes of professional development exploring teachers' perceptions of themselves as writers and writing teachers and their students' attitude. *English Teaching: Practice and Critique*, 12(3),137-156.Retrieved from <http://education.waikato.ac.nz/research/files/etpc/files/2013v12n3art8.pdf>

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

Antilla, J.A (2013). *The effects of early literacy development on academic success in the educational setting and implications for educational leaders and teachers*. Retrieved from

https://www.nmu.edu/education/sites/DrupalEducation/files/UserFiles/Antilla_Julie_MP.pdf

Applebee, A., & Langer, J. (2011). A snapshot of writing instruction in middle schools and

high schools. *English Journal*, 100, 14–27. Retrieved from

<https://s16491.pcdn.co/wpcontent/uploads/2017/05/snapshot.pdf>

Ashcroft, J. (2017). Do boys' attitudes to reading differ to those of girls? A study into the views of reading within a year three class. *The STeP Journal*, 4 (1), 2-14. Retrieved from

<https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/2811499f56e2a963fa161996504b1dcde76f9cd4.pdf>

Atkinson, C. (2009). Promoting high school boys' reading engagement and motivation: The role of the school psychologist in real world research.

School Psychology International, 30(3), 237-254. DOI:

10.1177/0143034309106494.

Blair, H. A., & Sanford, K. (2004). Morphing literacy: Boys reshaping their school based literacy practice. *Language Arts*, 81(6).

DOI=10.1.1.125.5159&rep=rep1&type=pdf

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

- Baines, T.J., Taylor, N.C., & Vanclay, F. (2013). Principles for ethical research involving humans: Ethical professional practice in impact assessment. *Impact Assessment and Project Appraisal*, 31, 243-243. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1080/14615517.2013.850307>
- Barbousas, J., & Velluto, R. (2017). "Silencing reading, silencing the boys: Using action research to investigate silent reading programs and its effects on boys' literacy skills. *Networks: An Online Journal for Teacher Research*, 15(1). Retrieved from <https://dx.doi.org/10.4148/2470-6353.1069>
- Boche, B. (2014). Multiliteracies in the classroom: Emerging conceptions of first-year teachers. *Journal of Language and Literacy Education*, 10(1), 114-135. Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1030724.pdf>
- Berrill, D., & Martino, W. (2003). Boys, schooling and masculinities: Interrogating the 'right' way to educate boys. *Educational Review*, 55(2). Retrieved from <http://www.tansfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/0013191032000072164>
- Biddulph, S. (2008). *Raising boys*. (3rd ed.). Sydney: Finch.

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

- Booth, D., & Elliot –Johns, S.E. (2009). *Current research and classroom practice: Toward more inclusive approaches to literacy development in schools*. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/229012467_Current_Research_and_Classroom_Practice_Toward_More_Inclusive_Approaches_to_Literacy_Development_in_Schools
- Boys Reading Commission. (2012). *The report of the all-party parliamentary literacy group commission*. Retrieved from https://cdn.literacytrust.org.uk/media/documents/2012_06_01_free_other_-_boys_commission_report.pdf.pdf
- Brown, D. (2015). *These heads are packed with stories: The out-of-school writing experiences of elementary age boys*. (Doctoral dissertation, Georgia State University, United States). Retrieved from https://scholarworks.gsu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1007&context=mse_diss&httpsredir=1&referer=
- Brown, G. (2009). Document analysis as a qualitative research method. *Qualitative Research Journal*,9(2). DOI: 10.3316/QRJ0902027
- Canadian Council on Learning. (2009). *Why boys don't like to read: Gender differences in reading achievement*. Retrieved from <http://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED519285>
- Clark, C. (2012). *Boys reading commission*. Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED541405.pdf>

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

Clark, C., & Burke, D. (2012). *Boys' reading commission. A review of existing research to underpin the commission*. London: National Literacy Trust.

Clark, C. (2016). Children's and young People's writing in 2015. Findings from the national literacy trust's annual survey. Retrieved from https://cdn.literacytrust.org.uk/media/documents/2016_11_03_free_research_-_writing_2015_-_final_bjO2ljN.pdf

Cohen, L. Manion, L. & Morrison K. (2000). *Research Methods in Education*. London: Routledge Falmer.

Coles, M. & Hall, C. (2002). Gendered readings: Learning from children's reading choices. *Journal of Research in Reading*,25,96-108. Retrieved from <https://doi/10.1111/1467-9817.00161>

Collins. (n. d). Perspectives. In Collins.com dictionary. Retrieved on April20,2020 from <https://www.collinsdictionary.com/dictionary/english/perspective>

Compton-Lilly, C. (2009). *Breaking the silence: Recognizing the social and cultural resources students bring to the classroom*. Newark: International Reading Association.

Creswell, J. W. (2008). *Research design: qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods approaches*. London: Sage Publications

Creswell, J.W., & Miller, D.L. (2000). Determining validity in qualitative inquiry. *Theory into Practice* ,39(3),123-131. Retrieved from https://people.ucsc.edu/~ktellez/Creswell_validity2000.pdf

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

- Curtin, M., & Fossey, E. (2007). Appraising the trustworthiness of qualitative studies: Guidelines for occupational therapists. *Australian Occupational Therapy Journal*, 54(2), 88-94. DOI: 10.1111/j.1440-1630.2007.00661.x
- Dagar, V., & Yadav, A. (2016). Constructivism: A paradigm for teaching and learning. *Arts and Social Sciences Journal*, 7(4). DOI: 10.4172/2151-6200.1000200
- Daley, J. A. (1979). Writing apprehension in the classroom: Teacher role expectancies of the apprehensive writer. *Research in the Teaching of English*, 13(1), 37-44. Retrieved from <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ204421>
- Darwish.H.(2016). Teachers attitudes and techniques towards ESL writing in Egyptian secondary schools. *International Journal for 21st Century Education*, 3(1), 37-57. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/311412491_TEACHERS'_ATTITUDES_AND_TECHNIQUES_TOWARDS_EFL_WRITING_IN_EGYPTIAN_SECONDARY_SCHOOLS
- DeMunck, V. C. & Sobo, E. J. (Eds.). (1998). *Using methods in the field: a practical introduction and casebook*. Walnut Creek, CA: AltaMira Press
- Dutro, E. (2001). "But that's a girls' book!": Exploring gender boundaries in children's reading practices. *The Reading Teacher*, 55(4), 376-384. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/290939337_But_that's_a_girls'_book_Exploring_gender_boundaries_in_children's_reading_practices

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

- Edmund-Woods, M. (2011). *A literature review exploring academic underachievement among males in the Trinidad and Tobago school system*. (Master's Thesis, University of Wisconsin-Stout, United States)
Retrieved from
<http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.389.7877&rep=rep1&type=pdf>
- Edwards, G., & Jones, J. (2018). Boys as writers: perspectives on the learning and teaching of writing in three primary schools. *Literacy*,52(1). Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1111/lit.12122>
- Eliot, L. (2009). *Pink brain, blue brain: How small differences grow into troublesome gaps—and what we can do about it*. Boston: Houghton Mifflin Harcourt
- Emig, J. (1977). Writing as a mode of learning. *College Composition and Communication*, 28(2),122-128. Retrieved from
<http://links.jstor.org/sici?sici=0010-096X%28197705%2928%3A2%3C122%3AWAAMOL%3E2.0.CO%3B2-H>
- Epstein, J.L. & Sanders, M.G. (2006). Prospects of change: Preparing Educators for school, family and community partnerships. *Peabody Journal of Education*, 81(2), 81-120.Retrieved from
<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/03004430500063747>

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

- Eskelä-Haapanen, S., Yikealo, D., Hasan, M., Simon, T., Okbaghebiel, G., Mekonnen, N., & Mengisteab, Y. (2018). *Parental involvement in children's literacy and numeracy skill acquisition*. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/322404381_Parental_involvement_in_children's_literacy_and_numeracy_skill_acquisition
- Fosnot, C.T. (eds). (2005). *Constructivism: Theory, perspectives and practice*. New York: Teachers College Press.
- Fraenkel, J. R., & Wallen, E. W. (2008). *How to design and evaluate research*. Boston: McGraw-Hill Higher Education.
- Gentry, J., & McAdams, L. (2013). Digital Story Expressions: Blending Best Practices in Literacy and Technology with Middle School Students. In *Proceedings of Society for Information Technology & Teacher Education International Conference 2013* (pp. 4253-4257). Chesapeake, VA: AACE. Retrieved from <http://www.editlib.org/p/48794>
- George, J., Quamina-Aiyejina, L., Cain, M., & Mohammed, C. (2009). Gender issues in education and intervention strategies to increase participation of boys. Retrieved from <https://www.mona.uwi.edu/cop/sites/default/files/GEORGE%20J%202009%20Gender%20Issues%20in%20Education%20and%20Intervention%20Strategies%20to%20Increase%20participation%20of%20Boys.pdf>

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

- Geske, A., & Ozola, A. (2009). Different influence of contextual educational factors on boys' and girls' reading achievement. *US-China Education Review*, 6(4), 38-44. Retrieved from <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=505734>
- Gest, S.D., Freeman, N.R., Domitrovich, C.E. & Welsh, J.A. (2004). Shared book reading and children's language comprehension skills: the moderating role of parental discipline practices. *Early Childhood Research Quarterly* 19, 319-336. DOI: 10.1016/j.ecresq.2004.04.007
- Graham, S. (2019). Changing How Writing Is Taught. *Review of Research in Education* 43, 277–303. DOI: 10.3102/0091732X18821125
- Graham, S. (2008). Effective Writing instructions for all students. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/242695295_Effective_Writing_Instruction_for_All_Students
- Graham, S., Cappizi, A., Harris, K. R., Hebert, M., & Morphy, P. (2014). Teaching writing to middle school students: A national survey. *Reading & Writing: An Interdisciplinary Journal*, 27, 1015–1042. DOI 10.1007/s11145-013-9495-7
- Graham, S., & Ng, C. (2017). *Engaging readers in the twenty-first century: What we know and need to know more*. Retrieved from <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/0296/3741bef3fdd9cb15d46cec1cfe6c49258ea9.pdf>
- Graham, S., & Rijlaarsdam, G. (2016). Writing education around the globe. *Reading Writing: An Interdisciplinary Journal*, 29, 781–792. DOI 10.1007/s11145-016-9640-1

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

Gray, D. E. (2004). *Doing Research in the Real World*. London: SAGE Publications.

Gove, A., & Wetterberg, A. (2011). The Early Grade Reading Assessment: An introduction. In A. Gove & A. Westerberg (Eds.), *The Early Grade Reading Assessment: Applications and interventions to improve basic literacy* (pp. 1–37). Research Triangle Park, NC: RTI Press.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.3768/rtipress.2011.bk.0007.1109>

HEART Trust. (n.d). Jamaica national report on technical and vocational education and training(TVET). Retrieved from
https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---americas/---ro-lima/---sro-report_of_spain/documents/meetingdocument/wcms_306332.pdf

Hughes-Hassell, S., Barkley, H.A., & Koehler, E. (2009). *Promoting equity in children's literacy instruction: Using a critical race theory framework to examine transitional books*. Retrieved from
http://www.ala.org/aasl/sites/ala.org.aasl/files/content/aaslpubsandjournals/slr/vol12/SLMR_PromotingEquity_V12.pdf

Hyatt, K. (2002). *Literacy outside school more real for boys. Teaching & learning*. Retrieved
from <http://www.muza.maine.nea.org/dir4/boysliteracy.htm>

Ice, C., & Hoover-Dempsey, K. V. (2010). Linking parental motivations for involvement and student proximal achievement outcomes in

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

homeschooling and public schooling settings. *Education and Urban Society*, 43, 339-369. DOI: 10.1177/0013124510380418

Jones, S., & Myhill, D. (2004). Seeing things differently: teachers' constructions of underachievement. *Gender and Education*, 16(4). Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1080/09540250042000300411>

Kaiser, A., Haller, S., Schmitz, S., & Nitsch, C. (2009). On sex/gender related similarities and differences in fMRI language research. *Brain Research Reviews*, 61, 49–59. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.brainresrev.2009.03.005>

Kehler, M., & Martino, W. (2007). Gender-Based literacy reform: A question of challenging or recuperating gender binaries. *Canadian Journal of Education*, 30(2), 406-431. Retrieved from <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ780771>

Kervin, L., & Mantei J. (2010). Incorporating technology within classroom literacy experiences. *Journal of Literacy and Technology*, 11(3), 77-100. Retrieved from <https://ro.uow.edu.au/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?referer=https://www.google.com/&httpsredir=1&article=1352&context=edupapers>

Kivunja, C. (2014). Theoretical perspectives of how digital natives learn. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 3(1). Doi:10.5430/ijhe.v3n1p94

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

- Kivunja, C &, Kuyini, A. (2017). Understanding and applying research paradigms in educational contexts. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 6(5). Retrieved from <https://ijhe.sciedupress.com>
- Landt, S. M. (2013) Books for boys: Multicultural literature with strong male characters. *International Journal of Multicultural Education*, 15(1). Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/full text/EJ1105050.pdf>
- Leedy, P. D., & Ormrod, J. E. (2010). *Practical research: planning and design* (9 ed.). Boston: Pearson Educational International.
- Lewis, Y.E (2010). *Literacy in elementary school in Jamaica: The case of the grade four literacy test*. (Doctoral dissertation, University of Iowa, United States). Retrieved from <https://ir.uiowa.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1883&context=etd>
- Literacy, numeracy results show girls out -mastering boys. (2018, January 12). *Jamaica Observer*. Retrieved from http://www.jamaicaobserver.com/career-education/literacy-numeracy-results-show-girls-outmastering-boys_122279
- Lincoln, Y.S., & Guba, E.G. (1985). *Naturalistic Inquiry*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage Publications.
- LMLP. (2019). Enrollment and output. Training Programme. Retrieved from <https://lmip.heart-nta.org/ETI.aspx>

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

- Logan, S., & Johnson, R.S. (2009). Gender differences in reading abilities and attitudes: Examining where these differences lie. *Journal of Research in Reading, 32*(2),199 –214. DOI: 10.1111/j.1467-9817.2008.01389.x
- Lynn, R., & Mikk, J. (2009). Sex differences in reading achievement. *Trames, 13*, 3–13. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.3176/tr.2009.1.01>
- Martino, W., & Kehler, M. (2007). Gender-based literacy reform: A question of challenging or recuperating gender binaries. *Canadian Journal of Education, 30*(2), 406–431. DOI: 10.2307/20466644
- Maxwell, J. A. (2012). *Qualitative research design: An interactive approach*. London: Sage.
- Millard, E. (2001). *Boys, girls and writing*. Retrieved from <http://www.literacytrust.org.uk/Pubs/millard.html>
- McGeown, S. P., Johnston, R. S., Walker, J., Howatson, K., Stockburn, A., & Dufton, P. (2015). The relationship between young children’s enjoyment of learning to read, reading attitudes, confidence and attainment. *Educ Res, 57*, 389–402.
DOI:10.1080/00131881.2015.1091234
- Mead, M. (2012). *Reading motivation: The difference between boys and girls and their reading preferences* (Master’s Thesis, St. Johns Fisher College, United States).Retrieved from <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/7860/77ef2810742163540caf349898952402f7fb.pdf>

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

- Mellati, M., & Khademi, M. (2018). Exploring teachers' assessment literacy on learner writing achievement and implications for teacher development. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 43(6). DOI: 10.14221/ajte.2018v43n6.1
- Merisuo-Storm, T. (2006). Girls and boys like to read and write different texts. *Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research*, 50(2), 111–125. DOI: 10.1080/00313830600576039
- Mertler, C. A. (2003). *Pre-service versus in-service teachers' assessment literacy: Does classroom experience make a difference?* Paper presented at the Annual Meeting of the Mid-Western Educational Research Association, Columbus.
- Milian, M. (2015). Reformulation: A means of constructing knowledge in shared writing. *Educational Studies in language and literature*, 5, 335-351. DOI :10.1007/S10674-005-8560-9
- Ministry of Education Youth and Culture. (2018). *Preliminary notes on the Caribbean advanced proficiency examination (CAPE) results for 2018*. Retrieved from <https://moey.gov.jm/sites/default/files/Notes%20on%20CAPE%20and%20CSEC%20Performance%202018.pdf>

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

Montero –Fleta, B., & Perez –Sabater, C. (2011). Knowledge construction and knowledge sharing: A wiki-based approach. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 28, 622-627.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.11.118>

Muszak, K.N. (2016). *Exploring the literacy lives of elementary male readers*.

Retrieved from

https://digitalcommons.brockport.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1685&context=ehd_theses

Nehal, M. (2017). *Parental involvement in the development of reading among grade R children in an Indian community*. (Doctoral dissertation,

University of KwaZulu-Natal, Pietermaritzburg, South Africa) Retrieved from

<https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/bb0e/5b4283a11d52c56bee63e3f1fbe0d90dc391.pdf>

Nieuwenhuis, J. (2007). Qualitative research designs and data gathering techniques. In K. Maree (Ed.), *First steps in research* (pp. 70-97).

Pretoria: Van Schaik Publishers

Olinghouse, N., & Graham, S. (2009). The relationship between the discourse

knowledge and writing performance of elementary-grade students. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 101(1), 37-50. DOI: 10.1037/a0013462

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

- Peal, S. (1980). Understanding Composing. National Council of Teachers of English. *College Composition and Communication*, 31(4), 363-369. Retrieved from <https://composingthoughts.qwriting.qc.cuny.edu/files/2011/01/Perl.pdf>
- Picton, I. (2019). *Teachers' use of technology to support literacy in 2018*. Retrieved from https://literacytrust.org.uk/documents/2371/Teachers_Use_of_Technology_report.pdf.
- Popham, W. J. (2009). Assessment literacy for teachers: Faddish or fundamental? *Theory into Practice*, (48), 4–11. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1080/00405840802577536>
- Rahman, S. (2017). The advantages and disadvantages of using qualitative and quantitative approaches and methods in language “testing and assessment” research: A literature review. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 6(1). DOI:10.5539/jel.v6n1p102
- Reid, R. (2012, November 25). The next 50 years –Save out boys. *Jamaica Gleaner*. Retrieved from <http://jamaica-gleaner.com/gleaner/20121125/lead/lead8.html>
- Reynolds, M. R., Scheiber, C., Hajovsky, D. B., Schwartz, B., & Kaufman, A. S. (2015). Gender differences in academic achievement: Is writing an exception to the gender similarities hypothesis? *The Journal of Genetic*

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

Psychology, 176, 211–234. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/00221325.2015.1036833>

Rintaningrum, R. (2009). *Investigating the performance of reading literacy achievement in grade 3 primary school students in south Australia.*

Retrieved from

https://www.academia.edu/38470458/Investigating_the_Performance_of_Reading_Literacy.pdf

Sang, Y. (2017). Expanded territories of “literacy”: New literacies and multiliteracies. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 8 (8). Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1139059.pdf>

Santangelo, T., & Olinghouse, N.G. (2014). *Effective writing instruction for students who have writing difficulties* Retrieved from <https://cedar.education.ufl.edu/wp-content/uploads/2014/10/Article-2.pdf>

Scardamalia, M., Sun, Y., & Zhang, J. (2010). *Developing Deep Understanding and Literacy while Addressing a Gender-Based Literacy Gap.* Retrieved from <http://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ910453.pdf>

Scott, A (2012). *Boys and writing: A look into attitudes and perceptions.*

(Master’s Thesis, St. John Fisher College) Retrieved from

<https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/5698/743595487356bbd03355796610f7ef31bc60.pdf>

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

- Sectorial Presentation (2014). *Student achievement*. Retrieved from <https://moey.gov.jm/sites/default/files/HMEsectoralD21-May7-2.pdf>
- Sharma, G. (2017). Pros and cons of different sampling techniques. *International Journal of Applied Research*, 3(7), 749-752. Retrieved from <https://www.allresearchjournal.com>
- Simonds, K.E. (2012). Parental Involvement and the impact on students' literacy development. (Master's Thesis, St. John Fisher College, United States). Retrieved from https://fisherpub.sjfc.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1220&context=education_ETD_masters
- Stanovich, K.E. (1986). Matthew effects in reading: Some consequences of individual differences in the acquisition of literacy. *Reading Research Quarterly*, 21, 360-406 https://www.psychologytoday.com/files/u81/Stanovich__1986_.pdf
- Stephen L., Schensul, Jean J., & LeCompte, Margaret D. (1999). *Essential ethnographic methods: observations, interviews, and questionnaires*. Walnut Creek, CA: AltaMira Press.
- Taherdoost, H. (2016). *Sampling methods in research methodology; How to choose sampling technique for research*. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/319998246>

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

Task Force on Educational Reform Jamaica. (2014). Retrieved from

<https://jis.gov.jm/estp/docs/Reports/JA%20Education%20Reform%20TaskForce%202004.pdf>

The Common Wealth Policy Brief. (2017). *Engaging boys for active citizenship*

through education .Retrieved from [https://www.thecommonwealth-educationhub.net/wp-](https://www.thecommonwealth-educationhub.net/wp-content/uploads/2016/01/Boys_Underachievement_Brief_201706.pdf)

[content/uploads/2016/01/Boys_Underachievement_Brief_201706.pdf](https://www.thecommonwealth-educationhub.net/wp-content/uploads/2016/01/Boys_Underachievement_Brief_201706.pdf)

The University of Technology. (2015). Student demographics: Annual Report

2013-2014. Retrieved from <https://www.utech.edu.jm/about-utech/history-1/AnnualReport201314.pdf>

The University of the West Indies. (2018). *Statistical digest 2012/13 to 2016/17*.

Retrieved <https://www.mona.uwi.edu/principal/departments/opair/uwi-statistical-digest>

The World Bank. (2008). *Youth at risk in the Latin America and the Caribbean*.

Retrieved from

<http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/en/245731468276337697/pdf/448230PUB0Box3102008009780821375204.pdf>

Then, K.L., Ali, E., & Ranking, J. (2014). *Focus group research: what is it and*

how can it be used? Retrieved from

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/261065206_Focus_group_research_what_is_it_and_how_can_it_be_used

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

- USAID. (2016). *Boys underachievement in education: A review of the literature with a focus on reading in the early years*. Retrieved from http://www.ungei.org/Boys_Underachievement.pdf
- USAID. (2011). *Masculinity and educational performance: Engaging our boys in the classroom*. Retrieved from https://www.mona.uwi.edu/cop/sites/default/files/consolidated_reply_files/EduExchange_Summary_3_Final_0.pdf
- USAID. (2019). *Study of barriers to access and completion of tertiary technical education in Jamaica*. Retrieved from <https://www.advanceprogram.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/04/SBAC-Jamaica-FINAL-for-Distribution.pdf>
- Uusen, A (2009). Changing teachers` attitude towards writing, teaching of writing and assessment of writing. *Problems of Education in the 21st Century* 10, 100-108. Retrieved from <http://www.scientiasocialis.lt/pec/node/194>
- Verberg, C. P. M., Tigelaar, D. E. H., & Verloop, N. (2015). Negotiated assessment and teacher learning: An in-depth exploration. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 49, 138-148. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2015.03.007>
- Vision 20/30 Jamaica. (2009). Education draft sector plan. Retrieved from https://planipolis.iiep.unesco.org/sites/planipolis/files/ressources/jamaica_vision_2030_education_sector_plan.pdf

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

- Vissak, T. (2010). Recommendations for Using the Case Study Method in International Business Research. *The Qualitative Report 15(2)*, 370-388. Retrieved from <http://www.nova.edu/ssss/QR/QR15-2/vissak.pdf>
- Vygotsky, L.S. (1962). *Thought and language*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- Weigel, D. J., Martin, S. S., & Bennett, K. K. (2006a). Contributions of the home literacy environment to preschool-aged children's emerging literacy and language skills. *Early Child Development and Care, 176*, 357-378. Retrieved from <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/03004430500063747>
- Whitehead, D. (2011). Can neuroscience construct a literate gendered culture? *English Teaching: Practice and Critique, 10*, (2), 78-87. Retrieved from <http://education.waikato.ac.nz/research/files/etpc/files/2011v10n2art6.pdf>
- Wilson, R.T. (2016). *Literacy and its significance in modern life*. Retrieved from <https://scholarworks.gvsu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1250&context=colleagues>
- Wongwanich, S., & Yamtim, V. (2013). A case of classroom assessment literacy of primary school teachers. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences 116*, 2998-3004. DOI: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.01.696

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

Rahman, K.F., & Yeasmin, S (2012) 'Triangulation 'research methods as the tool for social science research. *BUP Journal 1*(1),154-163. Retrieved from https://www.academia.edu/7019439/Triangulation_Research_Method_as_the_Tool_of_Social_Science_Research

Yilmaz, Y. (2013). Comparison of quantitative and qualitative research traditions: Epistemological, theoretical, and methodological differences. *European Journal of Education, 48*, (2). Retrieved from <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com-abs-ejed>

Zaidah, Z. (2007). *Case study as a research method*. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Zaidah_Zainal/publication/41822817__method/links/56a5938e08aeef24c58be1bf/Case-study-as-a-research-method.pdf?origin=publication_detail

123 RF. (n.d). *Concentrated young boy doing homework. Student doing math calculations*. [Photograph]. Retrieved from https://www.123rf.com/photo_70718408_concentrated-young-boy-doing-homework-student-doing-math-calculations-.html

123RF. (n.d). *Frustrated boy about how much he has to read*. [Photograph]. Retrieved from https://www.123rf.com/photo_70409792_frustrated-boy-about-how-much-he-has-to-read-.html

123RF. (n.d). *Happy student doing homework with a digital tablet*. [photograph]. Retrieved from https://www.123rf.com/photo_70358460_happy-student-doing-homework-using-a-digital-tablet-.html

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

123RF. (n.d). *Boy doing his homework against a white background.* [photograph]

Retrieved from https://www.123rf.com/photo_11686930_boy-doing-his-homework-against-a-white-background.html

123RF. (n.d). *Tired 8 years old boy doing his homework at the table. Child*

reading a book at the desk. Retrieved from [https://www.123rf.com/stock-photo/boy_reading_and_sad.html?](https://www.123rf.com/stock-photo/boy_reading_and_sad.html?oriSearch=boy+reading+and+happy&sti=latp0zmf7jdhocj8rq|&mediapopup=92629133)

[oriSearch=boy+reading+and+happy&sti=latp0zmf7jdhocj8rq|&mediapopup=92629133](https://www.123rf.com/stock-photo/boy_reading_and_sad.html?oriSearch=boy+reading+and+happy&sti=latp0zmf7jdhocj8rq|&mediapopup=92629133)

APPENDIX 1**Request to Gain Entry and Access to Research Site**

Bowers Wood

Bog Walk

St. Catherine

The Chairman

Board of Governors

Thru The Principal

_____School Name_____

Dear

Re: Request to gain entry and access

I am using this medium to seek permission to conduct a qualitative research at your institution. I am presently a final year student pursuing a Master's degree in Literacy Studies at the University of the West Indies. The research will be conducted over a six to eight-week period. The research topic under inquiry is: Exploring perspectives on the literacy underachievement of a group of boys at two rural primary schools in Jamaica.

For this research, several data collection methods will be employed. Hence I am requesting permission to observe and manually record literacy classes in session, audio record interviews with one literacy specialist, a class teachers and six male students taught by these teachers. I am also requesting permission to gain access to the grade four literacy data and to manually record the findings.

Participation in the study is voluntary. All participants, including students, teachers and school will remain anonymous in the study. The data collected will be kept strictly confidential, available only to my supervisor and myself and will not be used without the consent of all parties involved.

I am looking forward to a prompt and favourable response.

Your Truly,

Yonae Donald (Mrs.)

APPENDIX 2**Letter Requesting Participation in Research**

Bowers Wood

Bog Walk

St. Catherine

Dear Participant

Re: Participation in Research

This letter seeks to permission for your assistance as a participant in a qualitative research study relating to my master's degree in literacy studies at the University of the West Indies. As a requirement of the study, I am required to conduct audio recorded interviews as well as manually recorded observations of literacy classes in session. The topic under inquiry is: **Exploring perspectives on the literacy achievement of a group of boys at three rural primary schools in Jamaica**. The data collection period will span six to eight weeks. All interviews and observations will be scheduled at a time and place convenient to you.

Your privacy and safety is of utmost importance. All information gathered from the interview and observation is solely for the purpose of carrying out this study and will be kept confidential. You will remain anonymous in the written documentation of the study. Participation in this research is voluntary and can be terminated upon your request.

Yours Truly,

Yonae Donald (Mrs.)

Please read and sign complete the attached consent form.

I _____ agree to be a participant in a qualitative research study on the topic: **Exploring perspectives on the literacy achievement of a group of boys at two rural primary schools in Jamaica**. I agree to audio recorded interviews (30-60 minutes' sessions) as well as manual recordings of observations of literacy sessions with students. The purpose and nature of the research, as well as my role as a participant have been clearly explained to me and I willingly volunteer to be a participant.

APPENDIX 3**Sample Permission Letter for Parent/Guardian**

Bowers Wood

Bog Walk

St. Catherine

Dear Parent/Guardian:

Your child has been selected to participate in a research project being undertaken by myself, a graduate student at the University of the West Indies Mona. The aim of the study is to explore the perspectives of various stakeholders on the literacy achievement of boys at the primary level. Participation in this research project is voluntary. You may refuse to allow your child to participate or withdraw his participation at any point during the research project. Your child will remain anonymous and all information will be kept confidential.

If you are interested in allowing your child to volunteer, he will engage in three 30- minute audio recorded interviews involving two other grade five male students and the interviewer. The interview will be conducted in the month of February, 2019 at a time stipulated by the school. At the end of the group interview, your child may be selected for a 20-minute individual interview. I am looking forward to your favourable response to this letter.

Your Sincerely,

Yonae Donald.

Please read and fill out the permission slip below.

I _____ on the _____ of _____ do give permission

for my child _____ to participate in an audio taped group interview as well as an individual interview where necessary.

APPENDIX 4**Semi- Structured/Face to Face Focused Interview Schedule for Pilot**

This schedule was designed for interviews to be conducted with the male student participants

Research Topic: Exploring the literacy achievement of a group of boys at two rural primary school in question.

Name of Interviewer: _____

Date: _____

Duration: _____

Room: _____

Names of Interviewees:

_____/_____/_____

Questions

1. Describe how do you feel about reading?
2. Some people say that girls are better at reading then boys. What do you say about that?
3. How would you describe a good reader?
4. Describe how you feel when the language Arts teacher asks you to write?
5. Explain for me what writing classes are like.
6. Some people believe that girls are better writers than boys. What do you say to that?
7. How would you describe a good writer?

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

8. Do you have a phone, tablet or laptop?
 - b. What do you use it to do?

9. Explain for me what happens with reading and writing at your home.

APPENDIX 5**Semi- Structured/Face to Face Interview Schedule**

This schedule was designed for interviews to be conducted with literacy teachers and Classroom teachers

The questions may need to be modified as appropriate.

Research Topic: Exploring the literacy achievement of a group of boys at two rural primary school in question.

Name of Interviewer: _____

Date: _____

Room: _____

Duration: _____

Name of Interviewee: _____

Questions

1. For how long have you been serving as an educator at the primary level?
2. In what capacity do you serve at this institution?
3. Which grades do you presently teach?
4. What grades have you taught?
5. What is your area of specialization?
6. What professional training do you have in the field of education?
7. How would you describe the reading and writing performance of the children whom you have taught?

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

8. What would you describe as the factors contributing to the reading and writing performance of the students whom you have taught?
9. What has the school's approach to developing the reading and writing skills of the students at this institution?
10. What has been your approach to developing the reading and writing skills of students whom you have taught?
11. What do you perceive as to the role of writing in literacy development?
12. Technology is now closely aligned to literacy. What has been your experience in developing literacy in this digital era?
13. How would you describe the response of the school to the changing nature of literacy?
14. In recent times much attention has been given to the use of assessment in developing the literacy skills of students. What do you perceive as the role of assessment in this regard?

APPENDIX 6**Semi- Structured/Face to Face Focused Interview Schedule**

This schedule was designed for interviews to be conducted with the male student participants

The questions may need to be modified as appropriate.

Research Topic: Exploring the literacy achievement of a group of boys at two rural primary school in question.

Name of Interviewer: _____

Date: _____

Duration: _____

Room: _____

Names of Interviewees:

_____/_____/_____

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

Questions**Boys 'Reading Preferences /Boys' Attitude toward Reading**

Question 1: Choose the picture(s) which best describes you when you are asked to engage in reading.

Question 2. Explain why you choose the picture(s)

(Source: 123RF,n.d)

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

A wide cross section of books was placed on the table in front of the boys. They were asked to choose the books that are of interest to them. Types of book (books with large print and included pictures, comics, culture, insects, animals, Fairytale, books with boys as the main characters, books with girls as the main character, books which feature boys and girls as main characters.

Question 3: Here on the table are a variety of books.

- a. Which ones would you choose?
- b. Why did you choose those books?
- c. Explain why you did not choose the other books?
- d. Are there other kinds of materials that you find interesting to read?
- e. Explain why you find these kinds of material interesting.

Boys' Perceptions of Writing as a Gendered Activity/Boys Perception of themselves as Readers

1. If you saw a girl reading the books that you choose what would you say?
Explain
2. What if someone you heard someone saying that girls are better at reading than boys what would you say? Explain
3. How would you describe a good reader?

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

Levels of Reading Engagement

1. How often do you read in a week?
2. For how long do you read?
 - a. 15 minutes
 - b. 30 minutes
 - c. One hour
 - D. more than an hour
3. Where do you read? Explain why
4. Do you think it is important to be a member of a library? Explain
5. How often do you borrow a book from the library? Explain your reason
6. What kinds of book do you borrow from the library?
 - b. Explain why you choose those kinds of materials

Home/ Literacy Connection

1. Do you have a lot of books at home to read?
 - b. Tell me about the kinds of books/materials at your home.
2. How often in a week do you and your family members read these materials? Explain why
3. When you are reading, do you read alone or does someone else read to/with you?
 - b. Explain why
4. If someone else reads to/with you, who is it?
 - b. Explain why
5. How often does that person read to/with you?
 - b. Does the person read to/with you for
 - a. 15 minutes
 - b. 30 minutes
 - c. 1 hour
 - d. More than an hour

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

Use of Technology to develop literacy

1. Please raise your hands if you have a smart phone, tablet or a laptop?
 - b. What do you use them to do? Explain
2. Look at the list on the table and order them according how frequently you engage in these activities using your electronic gadget:
Play games, watch movies, watch music videos, send messages to friends, read.
 - b. Explain your reason for the ordering of the activities

Classroom Literacy practices

1. If I were to step into reading class one day, what kinds of book would you see your reading?
 - a. Would those kinds of books be interesting to you? Explain
2. What would you say if you were told that beginning tomorrow the reading teacher would use mainly electronic gadgets during reading class?
3. If you were the reading teacher for one day, tell me what reading class would be like

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

Perceptions and Attitudes towards Writing

Question 1: Choose the picture(s) which best describes you when you are asked to engage in writing.

Question 2: Explain why you choose the picture(s).

(Source: 123RF, n.d)

Boys perceptions of themselves as Writers

1. Do you see yourself as a good writer?
2. How would you describe a good writer?
3. Some people think that girls are better writers than boys? What are your views on that?

EXPLORING PERSPECTIVES ON THE LITERACY ACHIEVEMENT

Boys' Independent Writing Engagement

1. A diary and a journal were placed on the table and the boys were asked:
 - a. Do you know what these are?
 - b. Explain what they are used for?
 - b. Have you ever used any of them? When? Where?
 - c. Have you ever seen anyone in your class or at home using any one of these?
 - d. For what purpose was the person using the diary or journal?
 - d. What if you were offered one for free, would you take it and use it? Why?

Writing Instruction Practices

1. If I were to walk into writing class one day tell me:
 - a. What it is like if the topic is story writing
 - b. What it would be like if the topic was essay writing
 - c. What it is like when teacher tells you to write anything you want to write about
2. If you were the Language Arts teacher for a day, describe what writing class would be like.
3. What would you say if you were told that beginning tomorrow the Language Arts teacher would allow you to use your electronic gadgets during writing class?